

MODELING FRAMEWORK TO SUPPORT CRITICAL HABITAT IDENTIFICATION FOR THE WOOD THRUSH IN CANADA

Detailed Technical Methods and Results
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**BOREAL AVIAN
MODELLING
PROJECT**

**PROJET DE
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Abstract

A report describing detailed analysis methods, results, and conclusions of a modelling framework used to support identification of Critical Habitat by Environment and Climate Change Canada for a Threatened Species at Risk in Canada, the Wood Thrush (*Hylocichla mustelina*)

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Introduction and Objectives

Habitat loss has been identified as the primary threat affecting most species at risk (hereafter, “species at risk” [SAR]) of extinction in Canada. From 2006 – 2020, as the number of species listed on Canada’s Species At Risk Act (SARA) has increased from 488 to 814, 84 – 85 % of listed species were described as threatened or endangered by habitat loss and/or degradation (Venter et al., 2006; Woo-Durand et al., 2020). To stop further declines of individual species’ populations and then recover those populations, recovery plans are legally required to be drawn up within 1 – 2 years of listing species that are Threatened or Endangered. Part of recovery is identification of critical habitat (hereafter “critical habitat” [CH]), defined in Canada as “the habitat that is necessary for the survival or recovery of a listed wildlife species and that is identified in a recovery document for the species” (SARA, 2017; Lemieux Lefebvre et al., 2018). Legislation identifying and requiring protection of CH is a key component of protection and recovery of SAR of extinction in several countries (Endangered Species Act, 1973; Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act, 1999; SARA, 2017). The foundations of critical habitat are that: (1) densities of SAR are unevenly distributed across space with CH supporting disproportionately high densities, reproductive and survival rates (i.e., high-quality habitat) of a species, (2) population size is positively correlated with the amount of high-quality habitat, and (3) a minimum area of high-quality habitat is required to achieve a recovery target (Rosenfeld and Hatfield, 2006).

Despite the importance of habitat to species’ recovery plans, there remain challenges in identifying critical habitat, and many SAR in Canada do not yet have CH fully identified. In 2015, 13 % of listed Canadian species had critical habitat designation in place (Martin et al., 2017). In 2018, out of 158 vertebrate species’ populations listed as Threatened or Endangered, 63 % had recovery plans drawn up but only 38 % of these species had critical habitat designations (Lemieux Lefebvre et al., 2018).

Reviewing Life History Characteristics

The first stage of identifying important habitats for SAR is to review life history characteristics of the species of interest. The review will identify the habitat needs and other factors affecting survival and reproductive success that could cause declines in the first place or inhibit or enhance population recovery. One obstacle for many species that are at risk or suspected of being at risk is that there simply is not enough data due to a lack of sufficient field studies resulting from financial and logistical limitations (Jetz and Freckleton, 2015). For example, as of 2021, 11 % of freshwater plant and animal species in Canada are classified as at risk (Threatened, Endangered, or Extirpated) while 37.9 % of freshwater plant and animal species lack sufficient data to adequately classify their status as at risk or not at risk (DesForges et al., 2021). Nevertheless, several studies in which life-history models were trained on well-studied species — then were used to predict occupancy of poorly known species — estimated that a high proportion of these poorly known species are at risk of extinction (Howard and Bickford, 2014; Bland et al., 2015; Jetz and Freckleton, 2015). Environmental variables that are associated with life history traits and can be mapped spatially have been successfully used in some analyses to predict locations of species when data are limited and assess population risk of

such species, suggesting that data limitation may not be an obstacle to modelling to support CH identification (Brito et al., 2009; Hu and Liu, 2014; Teixeira et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2021).

Designatable Units and Management Units

The second challenge of identifying important habitats for SAR is to assess whether one or more population units of a species could benefit from being described and managed separately. Individuals from separate subpopulations within a species may be capable of reproducing with each other, but if populations are at least partially reproductively isolated from each other, there may be some genetic differentiation among populations and/or adaptations to local environmental conditions. The Committee on the Status of Endangered Wildlife in Canada (COSEWIC) defines subpopulations as “geographically or otherwise distinct groups in the population between which there is little demographic or genetic exchange (typically one successful migrant individual or gamete per year or less)” (<https://cosewic.ca/index.php/en-ca/about-us/definitions-abbreviations.html>). A declining subpopulation is unlikely to be “rescued” by individuals emigrating from other subpopulations of the same species, and such individuals may be ill-adapted to local environmental conditions. Differences in habitat use and genetic markers have been used to delineate Designatable Units (DU), which are management areas for species, subspecies, varieties, or genetically distinct populations, “...where such units are both distinct and evolutionarily significant” (<https://cosewic.ca/index.php/en-ca/about-us/definitions-abbreviations.html>). Examples of DUs include those for polar bears (Thiemann et al., 2008), lake whitefish (Mee et al., 2015), and caribou (Yannic et al., 2016). Individuals from separate DUs within a species may use different habitats, requiring land to be managed differently among DUs (e.g., woodland vs. mountain vs. barren-ground caribou). Determining habitat use in separate DUs is important to prevent the incorrect management prescriptions from being applied to a given DU. Apart from well-studied species like caribou and polar bears, the habitat needs of many SAR in Canada are not sufficiently well known to determine if more than one DU or management unit is needed for those species. However, it is likely that many wide-ranging Canadian species use habitat differently in different parts of their Canadian range. For example, Canada Warbler breeds in wet coniferous forests in eastern Canada and old deciduous forests in western Canada (Ball et al., 2016; Westwood et al., 2016; Crosby et al., 2019) and there is evidence of other boreal forest songbirds using habitat differently across Canada (Crosby et al., 2019). When differential habitat use is suspected, it is necessary to identify units of different habitat use such that the biophysical attributes of important habitat for SAR can be described appropriately. In the absence of genetic analyses and habitat studies for many less-studied SAR, there are modelling methods that can be used to objectively identify the number and extent of separate management units.

Assessing Population Risk: Estimating Existing Habitat and Population Sizes

The third challenge of identifying important habitats for SAR is assessing the amount of such habitat that currently exists and its ability to support the population and distribution objectives of SAR. For many species, identifying important habitat is based on where individuals and populations are currently known to occur or on the amount and locations of specific habitat features used by a species (Camaclang et al., 2015; Lemieux Lefebvre et al., 2018). This has

primarily been due to data limitations, which limits inferences that can be derived from habitat suitability and population viability models. Basing important habitat only on known occurrences and specific habitat features can underestimate the amount of habitat required by a species, because species may go undetected due to inadequate survey coverage of habitat, especially largely inaccessible and roadless habitats where traditional wildlife surveys are sparse or absent (e.g., much of the boreal region [Cumming et al., 2010; Van Wilgenburg et al., 2015]). Thus, important habitat has only been “partially” identified for most SAR in Canada, thus requiring additional studies before fully defining this habitat. For some SAR, there may be currently unoccupied sites that are both suitable and necessary for population recovery and long-term species survival (Thomas and Kunin, 1999; Camaclang et al., 2015). Another source of underestimation of habitat occupancy is that the probability of detecting species that are present within habitats is usually less than 1 (Denes et al., 2015). Thus, the amount of habitat required to maintain and recover populations of declining species is frequently underestimated. When potential habitat is based on abundance or occurrence of a species’ individuals, it can be estimated using species distribution models (SDMs) by relating abundance or occurrence of a species to environmental predictors that can be mapped in space (Elith and Leathwick, 2009; Denes et al., 2015). Maps (e.g., raster layers in a geographic information system) of the predictors can be stacked and the values of the predictors at a given location (e.g., pixel of known size at the same point on Earth’s surface in all the raster layers) are used to predict the density or abundance or (probability of) presence of the species there, after which the predictions are summed for the whole map to estimate population size (Elith and Leathwick, 2009). There is a wide variety of possible SDM types to use when estimating potential habitat and population size, based on the data available for a species (Elith and Leathwick, 2009), and SDMs have been successfully used to map potential habitat of poorly known species as well (Fois et al., 2018).

Assessing Population Risk: Accounting for Future Change in Habitat

Another challenge is that the amount and location of habitat for many Canadian species is likely to change in the future due to both future human land use (Foote and Krogman, 2006) and current ongoing natural disturbances and succession (Macias Fauria and Johnson, 2008; Brandt et al., 2013; Cumming et al., 2014), but also due to rising temperatures associated with climate change in Canada. Canada’s ecosystems are predicted to experience some of the highest temperature changes in the world (Shaver et al., 2000). Even in extensive relatively intact ecosystems like boreal forests in Canada, there are ongoing challenges in maintaining sufficient habitat for species like caribou (*Rangifer tarandus*) and boreal forest songbirds in the presence of current and proposed oil and gas development and forestry (Dyer et al., 2001, 2002; Wittmer et al., 2007; Leston et al., 2020). For ecosystems consisting of shifting mosaics of different vegetation like boreal forest (Macias Fauria and Johnson, 2008; Brandt et al., 2013), there must be enough habitat maintained for species dependent on certain stand types to ensure that current natural disturbances alone will not wipe out that habitat. Further, natural disturbances like fires and insect outbreaks are predicted to increase in frequency and intensity with global warming in Canada (Seidl et al., 2017; Navarro et al., 2018; Stralberg et al., 2018), which could decrease total area and average forest age of some boreal tree species and lead to large-scale conversion of boreal forest to deciduous forest, parkland, or grassland (Seidl et al., 2017; Navarro et al., 2018;

Stralberg et al., 2018; Cadieux et al., 2020). As a result, habitat set aside for species associated with older coniferous forests based on the occurrence of those species in present-day habitats will probably continue to decline with increasing human land use and climate change (Tremblay et al., 2018; Cadieux et al., 2020). In contrast to those SAR living in Canada's extensive boreal forests, most SAR in Canada have more limited distributions in southern Canada, where most land is currently developed for settlement and agriculture and relatively little land exists in protected areas (Kerr and Cihlar, 2004; Kanter, 2005; DeGuise and Kerr, 2006). Of these protected areas, few were established while accounting for effects of climate change on the ecosystems and species protected by those areas and there has been little or no adaptation of management in those protected areas in response to climate change (Scott and Lemieux, 2005). As of 2018, ongoing and probable future climate change were predicted to threaten habitat for 37.7% of SAR in Canada and up to 61.2 % of at-risk bird species (Woo-Durand et al., 2020). Thus, the identification of critical habitat requires consideration of the current and future natural disturbance dynamics, and their interactions with anthropogenic activities (Cadieux et al., 2019).

Where to Protect and Manage Habitat

Once current and potential future habitat conditions are predicted, these products can be used to inform the location and amount of habitat needed to support the population and distribution objectives for a SAR. Important habitats for SAR may occur in areas with high resource use and competing stakeholder interests (Palm et al., 2020; Westwood et al., 2020). Depending on the situation, a variety of options may be developed and presented to show how conservation of the most important habitats for SAR can be implemented spatially, using conservation-planning software decision tools (Moilanen et al., 2009). Designating areas with known occurrences of species is straightforward, but only relying on known locations ignores habitats where a species might occur but isn't confirmed to currently occupy, in part due to undersampling. Maps of predicted density may identify all currently suitable habitats within an area, but it is also important to consider locations predicted to be suitable in the future, especially if currently suitable habitats deteriorate with climate change. The relative importance of habitat connectivity, patch size, and edge effects on habitat quality for SAR differs among species. For species that are adversely affected by reduced habitat connectivity or increased habitat fragmentation, larger or better-connected habitats may be prioritized if such habitats allow more gene flow among populations or are less vulnerable to edge effects from adjacent unsuitable habitats (Moilanen et al., 2014). Conservation planners may only want to prioritize sites with suitable habitat if there is high confidence in predicted suitability. Biological factors guide the identification of critical habitat under SARA in Canada, and there are some situations, when habitat in Canada is not limiting to recovery, that socioeconomic factors can be considered (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2019). Ultimately, relevant government agencies make a recommendation to the federal Minister of Environment, who retains final discretion for accepting the definition of CH for a particular species and may choose to protect all or part of the recommended area of CH (Rosenfeld and Hatfield, 2006). The legal protection of CH under SARA applies only on federal lands. Outside of these lands, the identification of important habitats for SAR can still be used to inform land management and protection of species by other

means like provincial endangered species legislation and private conservation initiatives (Kanter, 2005).

Modelling Framework to Support Critical Habitat Identification by Environment and Climate Change Canada

Delays in identifying CH for SAR or important habitats for protection outside of SARA processes will result in further ongoing habitat loss, making it more difficult to recover those species' populations. However, hasty identification and designation of CH presents other risks, both the incorrect identification of suitable habitats and increased scrutiny and legal challenges of the designated CH by other stakeholders competing with SAR for the same lands (Rosenfeld and Hatfield, 2006). In other words, CH must be identified as quickly and transparently as possible for as many species as possible, but not so quickly that CH designations are thrown out in court challenges, leaving SAR to continue declining. Recently, a new modelling framework has been developed to support CH identification for SAR by ECCC (hereafter, "modelling framework to support CH ID") in a systematic, transparent, reproducible manner. The modeling framework is intended to provide well-founded, quantitative insight into important habitat for a species at risk, and these insights are expected to be useful to ECCC's process of identifying CH. Such a framework could result in designation of sufficient CH for protecting and recovering species at risk whose known locations likely represent only a small proportion of the actual amount of land that could be potentially occupied and required for persistence and present a roadmap for obtaining designations for more such challenging species.

- *Stage 1: Review life history characteristics.* Important life history characteristics of the species of interest are reviewed to identify predictor variables that are both associated with important habitats for the species and can be mapped across space.
- *Stage 2: Identify management units for assessing population risk.* An initial set of models is run on survey data for the species of interest within its potential distribution in Canada and possibly adjacent parts of the United States. The purpose of these models is to determine if the species of interest responds differently to the same habitat features (forest type, other land cover and human footprint types, forest stand age, etc.) in different parts of its range, and where the change in response occurs. Two or more separate management units for the species of interest are identified if that species responds differently to the environment in different parts of its range, and then a separate set of models is run in each management unit. Otherwise, the whole Canadian range of the species of interest can be treated as one management unit for generating predictive models.
- *Stage 3: Assess population risk.* A different set of models is run using the predictors identified in the Stage 1, using just survey data within the Canadian distribution of the species of interest. There are usually a wider variety of predictors available at national or smaller extents for predicting abundance. One model or a set of models is run separately for each management unit identified in the second stage. Once a final model is selected, that model is used to predict abundance of the species of interest in

different locations within the management unit. As predictors used in the models were mapped spatially, it is possible to create density distribution maps showing where the species of interest is currently most abundant and to calculate current population size for different areas. Given that the amount and locations of suitable habitat will change with future land use, forest succession, and climate change, land use simulation is used to create different land use and climate change scenarios exploring possible changes in the amount and location of natural and human disturbances, forest and other land cover types, forest age, and other predictors of habitat suitability. Future maps of predictor variables are then used to predict abundance of the species of interest in the future and assess population risk under different land use and climate change scenarios.

- *Stage 4: Spatial implementation.* Once maps of current and potential future distributions of the species of interest are generated, along with estimates of confidence in predictions, these maps are overlaid as inputs in conservation-planning software to rank locations from highest to lowest suitability for their contribution to supporting population and distribution objectives. The same software enables estimation of the amount of habitat that would be needed to maintain different proportions of the current population of the species of interest in each management unit.

The four-stage modelling framework for supporting CH identification presented here was originally developed for an at-risk bird species in Canada, the Canada Warbler (*Cardellina canadensis*). That species was selected to develop this framework because: 1) it is a species thought to have different breeding habitat requirements in different parts of its Canadian range (wet coniferous forests in eastern Canada [Westwood et al., 2016], old deciduous forests in western Canada [Ball et al., 2016]); 2) it is a declining species with most of its breeding range within Canada (COSEWIC, 2008; Environment Canada, 2016); 3) breeding habitat for this species in Canada is extensive but potentially vulnerable to climate change (eastern Canada: Taylor et al., 2018; Boulanger and Puigdevall, 2021; western Canada: Stralberg et al., 2018; Cadieux et al., 2020); 4) Canada Warbler is likely to respond very differently to harvest practices in western Canada (Ball et al., 2016; Hunt et al., 2017) versus eastern Canada (Chace et al., 2009; Goodnow and Reitsma, 2011; Becker et al., 2012; Westwood et al., 2016); and 5) there have been ongoing conservation planning exercises to model important areas for this species based on the amount and location of current and potential future breeding habitat in Canada (Westwood et al., 2020).

Objectives

The purpose of the current study described in this technical document is to assess how well the modelling framework to support CH ID performs when applied to another SAR in Canada, the Wood Thrush (*Hyalocichla mustelina*). Like the Canada Warbler, the Wood Thrush is a migratory songbird species that has experienced strong recent declines in North America (COSEWIC, 2012), and the Wood Thrush was listed as Threatened in the *Species of Risk Act* in 2017 (Species At Risk Public Registry, 2017). In contrast to the Canada Warbler, the Wood

Thrush has a more limited breeding distribution in Canada from southern Ontario and Quebec to New Brunswick and Nova Scotia. The Wood Thrush also nests in different forest habitats than Canada Warbler, mainly mature deciduous forests, but also uses swamps and requires some shrubland and younger forests as habitat for juvenile thrushes before migration. There is more existing habitat fragmentation due to urbanization and agriculture within the Wood Thrush range in Canada than in the Canada Warbler's primarily boreal breeding range. Finally, the deciduous forests used by Wood Thrush may respond differently to global warming than the breeding habitats used by Canada Warbler, the latter of which are projected to decline with a warming climate. A warming climate may reduce habitat for Canada Warbler in two different ways, depending on habitat preferences in different parts of its range: 1) replacement of wet coniferous forests used by Canada Warbler with deciduous forests in eastern Canada (Taylor et al., 2018; Boulanger and Puigdevall, 2021); and 2) conversion of older deciduous forests used by Canada Warbler in western Canada to younger-on-average forests or parkland and grassland (Stralberg et al., 2018; Cadieux et al., 2020). In contrast, Wood Thrush may respond positively to a warming climate in Canada since their deciduous forest habitats are likely to increase.

Study Area

The modelling framework to support CH identification for Wood Thrush used a study area larger than its Canadian range for reviewing life history characteristics of the species and identifying management units for Wood Thrush (eastern Canada, northeastern United States), a medium-sized study area for developing and running regional models of Wood Thrush density and distribution (the estimated Wood Thrush range in Canada), and small study areas (each province) in the Wood Thrush range for land-use scenarios and conservation-planning exercises. It was necessary to include the United States in the larger study area, as since most of the Wood Thrush breeding range in North America is in the eastern United States, most of the studies of this species' life history characteristics came from there as well. Some of the studies suggested a variable response of Wood Thrush to some habitat features in different parts of its range (e. g., elevation, flooding), which might make two or more management units for Wood Thrush in Canada more likely to be needed. Point count data from states adjacent or close to Canadian provinces with Wood Thrush were used in identification of management units so that Canadian point counts near the international border were less likely to be potential outliers in the analysis. Once management units were identified, an updated Wood Thrush distribution in Canada was determined and regional models were run for each management unit using just point counts from within the Wood Thrush range in Canada (Figures 1 – 3, Tables 1 - 2). As land use management may differ among provinces, land-use scenarios and conservation-planning exercises were conducted separately for each province.

Methods

Stage 1. Reviewing Life History Characteristics of Wood Thrush (*Hylocichla mustelina*)

The purpose of this review is to identify environmental variables affecting the distribution and life history characteristics that may be used to spatially predict abundance of Wood Thrush, for the purposes of creating species distribution models and projecting how habitat characteristics may change in the future.

The Wood Thrush is a Neotropical migratory songbird that breeds in various deciduous and mixed-wood forest types in eastern North America as far north as southeastern Ontario and Quebec and in New Brunswick, Prince Edward Island, and Nova Scotia. Preferred forest types are old and tall enough to include a sub canopy layer containing shrubs, shade, moist soil and leaf litter for foraging and nesting. Nests are typically located in a tree or large shrub ≤ 6 m above the ground although nests as high as 20 m have been documented (Evans et al., 2020). In forests where they co-occur with other thrush species, Wood Thrushes tend to occur and nest further from forest edge than American Robin (*Turdus migratorius*) and Hermit Thrush (*Catharus guttatus*), higher in trees than Veery (*Catharus fuscescens*), and at lower elevations than other species (Dellinger et al., 2007a). The Wood Thrush occupies more mature, warmer, drier forest sites than Veery (Bertin, 1977). In managed forest landscapes, Wood Thrush are more likely to use partially harvested deciduous stands than expected due to chance and will use regenerating even-aged stands if there are one or more tall (>18 m) residual trees in those stands (Dellinger et al., 2007b). In Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Wood Thrush were less abundant in historically logged forests (Simons et al., 2000). In South Carolina, Wood Thrush nests were encountered more often in bottomland hardwood forests than upland hardwood forests (Sargent et al., 2003).

In contrast to studies where Wood Thrush is associated with lower elevations (Simons et al., 2000; Sargent et al., 2003; Dellinger et al., 2007b), some early studies observed Wood Thrush associated with higher elevation further north in their range, during an early 20th Century northward range expansion (Tracy, 1943). Sargent et al. (2003) noted that while Wood Thrush were more abundant at lower elevations, this species was more common at the upland/bottomland interface in larger forests, possibly because floods made lower elevations poor habitat for Wood Thrush. Bertin (1977) speculated that Wood Thrush required moist forest soil conditions for supporting sufficient invertebrate prey, but Sargent et al. (2003) speculated that removal of leaf litter and understory vegetation by floods at lower elevations reduced prey availability and potential nest sites for Wood Thrush.

The Wood Thrush breeds in eastern North America but winters in the tropics, primarily in southern Central America. Decreasing availability of winter habitat is one likely mechanism underlying declines in this species (Stanley et al., 2014; Rushing et al., 2016). Locations of geolocator-tagged individuals indicate that over half of tagged Wood Thrushes overwinter in just one-third of the known wintering range for this species, in parts of Honduras and Costa Rica subject to heavy deforestation (Stanley et al., 2014). Wood Thrush abundance within Breeding Bird Surveys was correlated with the amount of forest habitat on wintering grounds in the year prior to a given breeding survey (Rushing et al., 2016). Breeding abundance was also correlated with climatic conditions on the wintering grounds in the year prior, as measured by the Enhanced

Vegetation Index, a composite measure of plant productivity and vegetation complexity (Rushing et al., 2016).

Arriving in April, female Wood Thrushes will typically attempt two broods per breeding season although 3-4 nest attempts may occur while trying to achieve two broods. Larger clutch sizes (3-4) are associated with earlier nesting attempts (Evans et al., 2020). Wood Thrushes are associated with mature forests and declined from forest stands after those stands were clear-cut or declined to a lesser degree in stands that were selectively thinned by forestry (Kendrick et al., 2015).

Several studies show mixed, inconsistent effects of forest fragmentation on Wood Thrush abundance and reproductive success. Wood Thrush are more likely to occur in larger forest fragments (Robbins et al., 1989) but will nest in fragments as small as 1 ha (Evans et al., 2020). Abundance is higher in landscapes with a greater proportion of forest (Richmond et al., 2012). In South Carolina, Wood Thrush nests were more likely in bottomland hardwood forests connected by corridors and were absent from upland hardwood forest fragments surrounded by fields (Sargent et al., 2003). Wood Thrush were observed to be less abundant at forest edges relative to forest interior in some studies, but the edge effect varied with edge type: Wood Thrush were less common at forest edges bordering paved roads relative to unpaved roads (Rich et al., 1994).

Wood Thrush nesting success tends to increase with increased surrounding forest fragment size and with nest distance from forest edge. In Delaware and Pennsylvania, nest success and productivity per successful nest were lower in forest fragments relative to nests in much larger forest tracts (Weinberg and Roth, 1998; Hoover et al., 2005). Along an urban-forest gradient in Pennsylvania, Wood Thrush experienced 58 % lower nest success along forest edges relative to nests in the interior of a large forest tract (Newell and Kostalos, 2007); however, in this same study urbanization and distance to edge were not useful predictors of Wood Thrush nesting success. In contrast, fragment size and distance to forest edge did not influence nest success in Ontario and Michigan populations (Friesen et al., 1999; Kaiser and Lindell, 2007), possibly because high forest fragmentation levels in those regions overwhelmed any distance-to-edge effects on survival. Forest fragment size was positively correlated with several physiological indicators of good health in Wood Thrush in Michigan (Niu, 2007). Total forest cover within the surrounding area positively influenced nest success (Driscoll et al., 2005; Richmond et al., 2012) but not in south-central Ontario (Burke and Nol, 2000), although nesting success increased in larger woodlots in the latter study.

Wood Thrush is parasitized by the Brown-headed Cowbird (*Molothrus ater*) in North America, and reproductive success is impacted by brood parasitism (Trine, 1998; Powell and Knutson, 2006). Cowbird parasitism of Wood Thrush can increase with increasing forest fragmentation (Lloyd et al., 2005) but parasitism rates are not consistent across the range of the Wood Thrush and are region-specific (Friesen et al., 1999; Trine, 1998). In Peterborough, Ontario, Wood Thrush experienced higher cowbird parasitism and nest prediction rates and lower seasonal productivity when nesting in woodlots with embedded houses relative to woodlots with adjacent houses (within 100 m) and undeveloped woodlots; however, lower nest success was not observed with embedding of houses in woodlots in Ottawa, Ontario, suggesting

that nest predation was region-specific (Phillips et al., 2005). As a result of parasitism and predation being region-specific (Roth and Johnson, 1993; Trine, 1998; Phillips et al., 2005), smaller fragments may serve as population sinks or rarely sources for Wood Thrushes in different regions.

Given negative effects of forest fragmentation, forest management for early successional shrubland birds in eastern North America at first glance may appear to conflict with management for Wood Thrush and other declining species associated with mature forests. However, early successional shrublands often serve as habitat for fledglings and juveniles of mature forest songbird species including Wood Thrush (Anders et al., 1998; Rivera et al., 1998), suggesting a second trade-off. Wood Thrush nest success, fecundity, and post-fledging survival did not differ between relatively unfragmented forests and forests fragmented by early successional shrublands rather than agriculture or urban land; in fact, breeding Wood Thrushes were more abundant in the forests with greater amounts of early successional shrublands (Schlossberg et al., 2018). Wood Thrushes respond positively to winter burning and thinning associated with forest management for Red-cockaded Woodpecker (*Picoides borealis*) habitat (Powell et al., 2000; Lang et al., 2002).

Early in dispersal, fledgling and juvenile Wood Thrush use forest-field edges (Anders et al., 1998), deciduous forests damaged by gypsy moth (*Lymantria dispar*) defoliation, and pine forests with dense deciduous understory (Rivera et al., 1998). Later in dispersal, juveniles may move back into older deciduous forests as fruits become available (Rivera et al., 1998). Fledgling and juvenile dispersal distances vary from 1-6 km from natal territories (Anders et al., 1998; Rivera et al., 1998; Lang et al., 2002). A study investigating 1-year time-lagged correlations between source and sink populations estimated natal dispersal distances in adult Wood Thrushes of 60-80 km over a year (Tittler et al., 2006).

Acid rain may affect breeding success of Wood Thrush, which were found to be less likely to breed in areas with more acid deposition, particularly at higher elevations or in areas with more forest fragmentation (Hames et al., 2002). Calcium-rich invertebrate prey like snails, isopods, and myriapods are important food items for Wood Thrush nestlings and successful fledging (Ladin, 2015), and such prey items may be reduced by acid rain in forests (Graveland, 1990), especially in northeastern North America where high levels of acid deposition have occurred over the past several decades (Hames et al., 2002). Reductions in calcium availability in soils, and calcium-rich prey (e. g., snails, isopods, and myriapods) can limit both egg production and nestling development, thereby limiting populations (Graveland and Drent, 1997; Pabian and Brittingham, 2011).

Post-fledging survival of Wood Thrush decreased with increasing drought, although drought effects declined in areas with increasing mature forest cover (Vernasco et al., 2018).

Based on investigations of Wood Thrush distribution and life-history characteristics on the breeding grounds, species distribution models for Wood Thrush in Canada should consider the following variables:

- *Cover by individual deciduous and coniferous tree species*, given that Wood Thrush are associated with deciduous and mixed-wood forests, but also that Wood Thrush may prefer deciduous tree species.
- *Forest height and forest age*, given that Wood Thrush are associated with mature and older forests. Variation in forest height and age may also be important: although Wood Thrush are considered sensitive to forest fragmentation in many studies, some studies suggest that patches of early successional or partially harvested forest may benefit Wood Thrush.
- *Canopy cover and variation in canopy cover*, given that both forest shade and dense shrubby growth may provide features for Wood Thrush, both as breeding adults and as dispersing fledglings and juveniles.
- *Different types of non-forestry human footprint* like roads, urban land, and agriculture. Wood Thrush are considered more sensitive to harder footprints such as these.
- *Elevation*, given that Wood Thrush are generally associated with lower elevations.
- *Wetness or likelihood of flooding*, given that while Wood Thrush may prefer forests growing in moist soils, wetlands and flooded forests may be unattractive environments for this species.
- *Soil types*, given that acidic or less-buffered soils may support forests that are poorer environments for Wood Thrush. Further, drier soils in more drought-prone may support fewer invertebrate prey for Wood Thrush, as might flooded soils.
- *Acid deposition*, given that acid rain in eastern North America may have degraded forest environments for Wood Thrush by reducing potential invertebrate prey.
- *Measures of forest intactness or fragmentation*, given that Wood Thrush are thought to be sensitive to forest fragmentation in many regions. A relatively simple metric might be the amount of suitable forest at larger spatial scales (1 km² or greater).

Stage 2. Identifying Management Units for Regional Modelling and Population Risk Assessment for Wood Thrush

To determine how to manage lands for SAR in Canada, ecologists and land use planners can examine how a species' abundance, survival, reproductive success, or individual fitness changes in response to values of environmental variables in part of the species' range. If abundance, survival, reproductive success, or individual fitness of a species increases with values of an environmental variable, then habitat for that species is predicted to be better where that environment variable's values are higher. The long-term prospects for that species are predicted to improve if the mean value of that environmental variable is increased – perhaps by land management - within the species' range. Similarly, if abundance, survival, reproductive success, or individual fitness of a species increases with values of an environmental variable, then the long-term prospects for that species will decline unless the mean value of that environmental variable is decreased within the species' range.

For environmental variables affecting species abundance, it is not reasonable to assume that such variables have a constant effect on a species everywhere that species occurs. First, there may be a biological basis for non-constant effects of environmental variables across space. A

species may use habitat differently at different ends of its distribution, or the effect of one environmental variable may be modified by the strength of another environmental variable. Second, given the extent of some spatial data sets, there may be differences in completeness, measurement methods or measurement accuracy for different regions in the study area, affecting data quality and ultimately how species respond to environmental variables associated with those data (Kala et al., 2017).

Statistical models usually account for such differences in a variable's effects by including terms for interactions with other variables, including explicitly spatial variables (e.g., latitude, longitude). Such models account for effect size changes when predicting a species' response to those effects; however, as statistical models generally estimate a constant effect size for each predictor on data used to generate the model, most models still cannot be used to estimate the explicit effect size of a given environmental variable in a particular part of the species' range. Another issue is determining where in a species' range there is a significant change in the species' response to a given environmental variable or combination of variables, i.e., where there is a change in how land should be managed for that species.

Geographically Weighted (GW) Regression Models

In contrast to most statistical models, geographically weighted (GW) regression and generalized linear models estimate a separate model coefficient for each environmental variable at each species' location (Fotheringham et al., 2002). The values of these model coefficients at different locations can be visualized in maps to see how a species responds differently to the same environmental variable across its range (Holloway and Miller, 2015; Kala et al., 2017; Shao et al., 2020). GW models (specifically, GW Poisson generalized linear models) were generated using the "GWmodel" package (Lu et al., 2014; Gollini et al., 2015) in R to examine how effect sizes of environmental variables on Wood Thrush change across this species' range in eastern Canada and the northeastern United States. Several recent studies have applied GW models to examine spatial variation in environmental variable effect size and importance on bird abundance and community metrics (Holloway and Miller, 2015; Kala et al., 2017, Shao et al., 2020).

Location data used in GW models are unlikely to be statistically independent of each other, and this is especially likely to be true for point count data distributed unevenly in space. GW models account for spatial autocorrelation in data by incorporating a spatial weights function as a model term. As in weighted least squares regression, GW models use a spatial weights function to average the influence of each observation on the model result with the influence of nearby points in space, downweighting the influence of more distant observations. The rate at which down-weighting occurs with increasing distance often follows a Gaussian curve but can follow other shapes like an exponential curve. Points beyond a certain neighborhood distance essentially have no influence on an observation's impact on the model result, and observations at least this distance apart are statistically independent of each other. Beyond accounting for spatial autocorrelation, the spatial weights function permits the calculation of a local model coefficient for each model predictor at each location, as opposed to a

single global model coefficient for each predictor as in most types of models (Holloway and Miller, 2015; Shao et al., 2020).

Point Count Data Collection

Point count data from both eastern Canada and the northeastern United States were used as potential observation data for GW models, after calculating QPAD detection offset variables for each observation (Table 1). Although modelling was intended to focus on population assessment of Wood Thrush just in Canada, Wood Thrush data from the northeastern United States were used in GW models to reduce the possibility of estimating extreme habitat responses by Wood Thrush to environmental variables at point count locations at the southern limit of the Wood Thrush's range in Canada (Figures 1 – 2).

Point count data came from the Boreal Avian Modelling Project (<https://borealbirds.ualberta.ca/>), North American Breeding Bird Survey (<https://www.pwrc.usgs.gov/bbs/>), the U.S. node of the Avian Knowledge Network (<http://avianknowledge.net/>) and other data sources in forested landscapes in eastern Canada (New Brunswick, Nova Scotia, Ontario, Prince Edward Island, Québec) and the midwestern and northeastern United States (Connecticut, Illinois, Indiana, Maine, Maryland, Massachusetts, Michigan, Minnesota, New Hampshire, New Jersey, New York, Ohio, Pennsylvania, Vermont, Wisconsin, West Virginia), within the breeding distribution of Wood Thrush. Using a larger area also would enable prediction of how Wood Thrush could respond to a warming climate in Canada by examining how Wood Thrush further south in the U.S. respond to climate variables.

Figure 1. Map of study area and point count locations used for geographically weighted regression models used to delineate potential management units for Wood Thrush in Canada. To prevent provinces and states with more point count coverage from dominating the analysis results, point counts were sampled from spatial blocks within the study area.

Figure 2. Map of study area and point counts with Wood Thrush detections used for geographically weighted regression models used to delineate management regions for Wood Thrush in Canada. Point locations in the map indicate point counts that were available for use in the analysis where at least one Wood Thrush was detected. To prevent provinces and states with more point count coverage from dominating the analysis results, point counts were sampled from spatial blocks within the study area.

For each bird survey visit used as an observation in GW models, an offset variable was calculated and included within models to account for detection probability differences among surveys due to survey time, time of season, survey methods, and probability of detecting more distant Wood Thrushes singing in different vegetation (Sólymos et al., 2013). The offset variables were generated with the QPAD package in R (<https://github.com/psolymos/QPAD/>), using model coefficients associated with Julian day (number of days since January 1), time since

sun rise, latitude, longitude, maximum distance noted for individual birds within a survey, and duration of each point count.

Table 1. Description and sources of point count data that were available for subsampling and use within geographically weighted regression models of Wood Thrush abundance in Canada and the United States.

Data Source	Description	Years	Comments
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	3 minute unlimited distance point counts collected in Chignecto and Tintamarre National Wildlife Areas, Nova Scotia	2015	
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	5 minute unlimited distance point counts divided into intervals collected in Acadian Research Forest, New Brunswick	2016	
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	5 minute unlimited distance point counts collected in Belle Isle National Wildlife Areas, Nova Scotia	2018	
Avian Knowledge Network (U.S.)	Georeferenced point counts collected on multiple National Wildlife Refuges by several different methods.	1992 - 2019	Obtained through agreement with Boreal Avian Modelling Project
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts, information combined with NB, NS and PEI Forest Resource Inventory data (Maritimes Breeding Bird Atlas).	2006 - 2010	
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts (Ontario Breeding Bird Atlas)	1981 – 1985; 2001 - 2005	
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts (Quebec Breeding Bird Atlas)	2010 - 2014	
Boreal Avian Modelling Project	Georeferenced point counts collected from dozens of smaller independent bird studies across boreal and hemiboreal forest regions using a variety of point count methods.	1993 - 2018	
Boundary Waters Canoe Area, Superior National Forest, Minnesota	10-minute point counts, all birds observed recorded within distance and time intervals. Collected by Gerald Niemi and Edmund Zlonis (researchers)	2010 - 2016	Obtained through agreement with Boreal Avian Modelling Project

Bird Conservancy of the Rockies National Ecological Observatory Network (US)	6-minute 150-m point counts arranged in clusters, part of Breeding Landbird Point Counts study in BART, HARV, SERC, STEI, TREE, UNDE Bird Conservation Regions	2015 - 2019	
CWS-Québec, Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)	20-minute 75-m point counts at Grand Marais and Lake St. Francis Wildlife Management Areas	2004 - 2006	
Forest Bird Monitoring Program	10 minute georeferenced point counts, unlimited distance in earlier years, 100-m point counts in later years. Collected by the Ontario provincial government.	1987 - 2019	
Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) Network	10-minute 50-m point counts in the Parker River National Wildlife Refuge, Plum Island estuary, Massachusetts. Collected by N. Pau (researcher).	1994 - 2002	
Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) Network	10-minute 50-m point counts collected in forest openings in Harvard Forest, Massachusetts by David King (researcher) as part of Bird Communities in Forest Openings study.	2014 - 2015	
Natural Resources Research Institute	10-minute unlimited distance point counts for Minnesota Breeding Bird Atlas and in Superior and Chippewa National Forests. Collected by Alexis Grinde (researcher).	2009 - 2019	
North American Breeding Bird Survey (Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC))	Georeferenced 3 min. point count (presence/absence) data collected by volunteers and professionals; survey routes w/i lat./long. degree blocks.	1993 - 2019	Used points from NB, NS, ON, PEI, QU.
North American Breeding Bird Survey (United States Geological Survey (USGS))	Georeferenced 3 min. point count (presence/absence) data collected by volunteers and professionals; survey routes w/i lat./long. degree blocks.	1993 - 2019	Used points from CT, DE, IL, IN, MA, MD, ME, MI, NH, NJ, NY, OH, PA, RI, VA, VT, WI.
Northeast Temperate Network and Vermont Center for Ecostudies	10-minute 50-m point counts collected from 6 New England states. Collected by Steve Faccio (researcher)	2005 - 2011	
Study: Breeding Bird Response to the Loss and Fragmentation of the Forest Cover in Eastern Ontario	Point count data collected by Remi Torrenta (graduate student)	2014 - 2015	remi.torrenta@ gmail.com

Study: Forested Wetland Birds	10 minute unlimited distance point counts. Collected by John Brazner and Laura Achenbach (researchers)	2015 - 2016	
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Predictor Data Collection

Predictors consisted of land cover, topography, and climate layers whose extent included both Canada and the United States, since point counts were used from both countries in GW models (Table 2). Land cover initially consisted of 19 land cover classes (CEC, 2005), but prior to modelling, the opticut package in R (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/opticut/index.html>) was used to condense the number of potential land cover predictors by combining land cover classes with similar mean densities of Wood Thrush. As an example, there were similar Wood Thrush densities predicted within barren lands and shrublands, so these land cover classes were combined into a single land cover class (“barren/shrub”). From these predictors, variables that were not strongly correlated with each other ($|r| < 0.7$) were selected to be used in a GW model with a Poisson error distribution:

Abundance ~ Elevation + land cover (agriculture) + land cover (barren land/shrubland) + land cover (coniferous forest) + land cover (deciduous forest) + land cover (developed land/wetland) + land cover (grassland/mixed-wood forest) + forest height + tree cover + roadside (0/1) + MWMT + MSP + CMI + detection offset

Table 2. Description and sources of predictor variables used in geographically weighted regression models of Wood Thrush abundance in Canada and the United States.

Variable	Description	Abbreviation	Citation
Land cover	Nineteen land cover classes for North America (250 m resolution) based on 2005 Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) satellite imagery; amalgamated into six land cover class combinations with similar Wood Thrush densities: 1) agriculture; 2) barren land/shrubland; 3) coniferous forest; 4) deciduous forest; 5) developed land/wetland; 6) grassland/mixed-wood forest.	Land cover	CEC 2005
Tree cover	Percent tree cover (30 m resolution) from Global 30 m Landsat Tree Canopy layer version 4	Tree cover	NASA Landsat Science 2019
Forest height	Forest canopy height (1 km resolution) defined as the distance between the beginning and the lidar ground peak of the recorded waveform.	Forest height	Simard et al. 2011

Roadside status	A binary variable to indicate a roadside (1) or offroad (0) survey location.	Road	Van Wilgenberg et al. 2015; Sóllymos et al. 2020
Elevation	1-km elevation raster associated with the climate raster geodatabase	elev	Wang et al. 2016
Mean Warmest Month Temperature	Average daily temperature in warmest month of the year in a given location	MWMT	Wang et al. 2016
Mean Summer Precipitation	Average monthly precipitation (mm) for summer months	MSP	Wang et al. 2016
Averaged annual Climate Moisture Index	Averaged annual climate moisture index, which is the difference between annual precipitation and potential evapotranspiration	CMI	Wang et al. 2016

Running the GW Models

There were 399,016 surveys with complete observations to work with in the study area. Since point counts were not distributed evenly through the Wood Thrush study area, and since some point counts include repeated visits within or across years, there is spatial and temporal correlation within the data. To reduce influence of areas with unusually high numbers of point counts or repeated point count visits on results, 10 sample data sets were generated by partitioning the study area into blocks of latitude and longitude and randomly sampled surveys with replacement from each block. Each sample data set contained 16,359 surveys and GW models were run using each sample data set.

GW modelling was done in two stages: first an initial round of modelling was done on one spatially random sample data set to identify the best kernel shape (whether to down-weight more distant point counts using a Gaussian or exponential curve), band width (neighborhood distance or number of “neighborhood” points to use in spatial weighting), and whether to use a fixed or adaptive band width. Based on this initial modelling round, a non-adaptive exponential kernel of 157 m was chosen for all 10 GW model runs, the model was run on 10 random sample data sets and values for each model coefficient at each point count location were calculated. After the 10 GW model runs, a 1-km-resolution raster was created for each model predictor, separately for each sampling data set. The 10 sample data set raster layers for each model coefficient were then overlaid and mean values were calculated for each model coefficient in each grid cell with Wood Thrush detections.

Cluster Analysis

The mean coefficient values at each grid cell location were then used in model-based cluster analysis (“mclust” package in R: Fraley and Raftery, 2002; Fraley et al., 2012). Although there were climate variables in the GW models, the mean effect sizes of interest in the cluster analysis were for those variables that humans have more direct influence over: elevation; land

cover categories (agricultural; barren/shrubland; coniferous forest; deciduous forest; mixed-wood forest/grassland; developed/wetland), tree cover, forest height, and roadside. Although effect sizes of individual variables on Wood Thrush abundance were compared among different clusters across the GW model study area, cluster analysis was mainly used to examine if the overall effect of these environmental variables on Wood Thrush abundance varies sharply in different parts of the study area. In such a case, then locations with similar overall effect sizes of multiple environmental variables will be assigned to the same cluster and locations within the same cluster will be located closer together in space than locations assigned to different clusters. If locations assigned to different clusters are well separated across the Wood Thrush's range, then there could be a biological basis for modelling and/or managing habitat differently for Wood Thrush in separate regions defined by these clusters. The number of clusters to use was assessed in two ways. First, each potential maximum number of clusters from 2 to 9 was treated as a separate Gaussian mixture model and the integrated likelihood or probability of each model was assessed using the model's Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) value. The model with the highest or most positive BIC value was judged to be the "best" model statistically speaking (Fraley and Raftery, 2002). Second, outputs (distribution maps of grid cell locations assigned to specific cluster values) were generated and examined for 2 to 9 clusters to see if clusters in certain regions were more frequently isolated from other clusters.

In addition to performing cluster analyses based on coefficient values for points from all 10 sample data sets, 3-cluster, 5-cluster, and 7-cluster analyses were run on individual sample data sets to assess the stability of cluster assignments (i. e. how much results shifted with different sample data sets). BIC plots were generated for each sample data set and cluster analysis. The locations of point count cluster assignments were mapped for each combination of sample data set and cluster analysis. Effect sizes (mean \pm standard deviation) were plotted for each GW model predictor used in the cluster analyses to see where there were significant differences in responses to environmental variables in different clusters.

Stage 3. Population Risk Assessment: Regional Models of Wood Thrush Abundance for Landis Scenarios

Point Count Data

To generate regional Wood Thrush abundance models, a subset of the point counts that were available for GW modelling was used. First, those point counts that occurred within Canada and contained at least one Wood Thrush detection were identified and used to calculate a Wood Thrush range boundary within Canada based on kernel density estimation methods (Lichti and Swihart, 2011), using the "ks" package in R (Duong, 2021). The range boundary corresponded to the 99 % line. Point counts available for GW modelling were filtered to those that occurred in Canada and within the kernel-density-estimated Wood Thrush range, thus excluding point counts in the United States, Prince Edward Island, and parts of northern New Brunswick, Nova Scotia, Ontario, and Quebec (Figure 3, Table 3).

Figure 3. Map of the study area and point counts with Wood Thrush detections used for regional boosted regression tree models for Wood Thrush in Canada. Study area boundary was estimated with kernel-density methods from these point counts with boundaries set at the 99 % probability contour.

Table 3. Description and sources of point count data that were available for subsampling and use within boosted regression tree models of Wood Thrush abundance in Canada.

Data Source	Description	Years	Comments
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	3 minute unlimited distance point counts collected in Chignecto and Tintamarre National Wildlife Areas, Nova Scotia	2015	
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	5 minute unlimited distance point counts divided into intervals collected in Acadian Research Forest, New Brunswick	2016	
Atlantic Canada Conservation Data Centre	5 minute unlimited distance point counts collected in Belle Isle National Wildlife Areas, Nova Scotia	2018	
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts, information combined with NB, NS and PEI Forest Resource Inventory data (Maritimes Breeding Bird Atlas).	2006 - 2010	
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts (Ontario Breeding Bird Atlas)	1981 – 1985; 2001 - 2005	
Bird Studies Canada (Nature Counts)	Georeferenced 5 min. point counts (Quebec Breeding Bird Atlas)	2010 - 2014	
Boreal Avian Modelling Project	Georeferenced point counts collected from dozens of smaller independent bird studies across boreal and hemiboreal forest regions using a variety of point count methods.	1993 - 2018	
CWS-Québec, Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)	20-minute 75-m point counts at Grand Marais and Lake St. Francis Wildlife Management Areas	2004 - 2006	
Forest Bird Monitoring Program	10 minute georeferenced point counts, unlimited distance in earlier years, 100-m point counts in later years. Collected by Ontario provincial government.	1987 - 2019	
North American Breeding Bird Survey (Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC))	Georeferenced 3 min. point count (presence/absence) data collected by volunteers and professionals; survey routes w/i lat./long. degree blocks.	1993 - 2019	Used points from NB, NS, ON, QU.
Study: Breeding Bird Response to the Loss and Fragmentation of the Forest Cover in Eastern Ontario	Point count data collected by Remi Torrenta (graduate student)	2014 - 2015	remi.torrenta@gmail.com

Study: Forested Wetland Birds	10 minute unlimited distance point counts. Collected by John Brazner and Laura Achenbach (researchers)	2015 - 2016	
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Boosted Regression Tree (BRT) Models

Boosted regression trees (hereafter, “BRT”s) (Elith and Leathwick, 2009) were used to build regional models of Wood Thrush abundance and distribution in eastern Canada. While abundance models for wildlife can be generated from many kinds of models (e. g. generalized linear models, mixed-effects models, etc.), BRTs were chosen for several reasons in the case of Wood Thrush, with most reasons relating to a greater interest in being able to predict where a species of concern is most abundant rather than understanding how and why that species’ abundance varies the way it does. First, a large amount of point count data is available for Wood Thrush, enabling the use of more predictors and modelling of non-linear responses to variables and interactions among variables. Second, BRTs can account for nonlinear responses to individual variables and interactions among individual variables “under the hood” without a lot of time spent by analysts explicitly modelling potential non-linear and interaction terms. Over larger regions where a species occurs and is modelled, a species’ response to environmental variables is likely to be modified by the presence of other variables. As the number of predictors used in modelling increases, the potential number of such terms that would have to be modelled greatly increases, so BRTs can be used to save much time and labour if obtaining predictions based on nonlinear responses and interactions is important. Third, BRTs have a good record for prediction accuracy, since cross-validation of prediction results is incorporated into the BRT modelling process. Fourth, BRTs are semi-parametric models robust to most violations of assumptions about error distributions, which could be important for point count data combined from many independent studies.

Categorical land cover data were obtained from Landsat satellite data (30-m resolution) by Agriculture Canada (AAFC, 2021) for the years 2011, 2015, 2020. These land cover data were used because of their recent origin and greater accuracy in representing forest and shrubland cover within agricultural and urban areas of eastern Canada (Table 4). To get a “local” estimate for each land cover type of interest (barren ground, coniferous forest, all cultivated land, deciduous forest, grassland, mixed-wood forest, orchards, shrubland, urban land, open water, all wetland), binary rasters were generated for each land cover type and Gaussian filtering (“focalweight” function in “raster” package [Hijmans et al., 2015]) was used to estimate the proportion of each land cover type within 150 m of each pixel (Chandler and Hepinstall-Cymerman, 2016). These proportions were then resampled and averaged at coarser resolution (150 m) to speed up processing, then additional Gaussian filtering was performed to obtain average land cover proportions within 250, 1000, and 2000 m of each pixel. Finally, land cover proportions at 150, 250, 1000, and 2000 m were resampled to 250-m resolution to enable stacking of these raster layers with other layers. The spatial scales at which land cover was averaged were based on the scales at which Wood Thrush was observed to respond to forest structure and cover in previous studies (Burke and Nol, 2000; Austen et al., 2001; Lee et al., 2002; Driscoll et al., 2005; Richmond et al., 2012; Bonnot et al., 2013) (Table 4).

Wood Thrush will use swamps as habitat separate from other wetland types, and the Agriculture Canada Landsat products may misidentify swamps as shrubland. Thus, a 30-m swamp raster layer was generated from separate provincial sources in which swamps could be distinguished from other wetland types. Depending on the source (Table 4), pixels were classified as swamps in the original raster (Ontario Land Cover Compilation v.2.0, 2016) or forested wetlands shapefiles (New Brunswick Department of Environment and Local Government, 2021) or swamps were identified as locations where forested shapefile polygons intersected with wetland polygons (Nova Scotia Department of Lands and Forestry, 2021). Once a 30-m raster layer was generated for each province in ArcGIS, then the same Gaussian filtering operations were performed on each provincial swamp raster as done for the Agriculture Canada Layers to generate raster layers of the proportions of swamp within 150, 250, 1000, and 2000 m of each pixel at 250-m resolution. These proportions were independent of the land cover proportions measured at each spatial scale (Table 4).

Forest stand age and biomass (branch, foliage, woody stem, bark, total dead, total live aboveground) were extrapolated from satellite data from 2001 and 2011 at 250-m resolution (Beaudoin et al., 2014), clipped to each region and extracted to point counts based on survey year (1993-2005 [N=145,957]; 2006-2020 [N=170,284]). The “local” estimates for stand age (#years since stand origin) and different fractions of live aboveground and dead biomass (tonnes/ha) were extracted from each 250-m pixel, then Gaussian filtering was used to estimate the average stand age and biomass within approximately 250, 1000, and 2000 m of each pixel (Table 4).

In each region, 6 BRT models were run differing in the potential predictors that were used. One BRT (the “full model”) included land cover, forest age, forest biomass, and swamp predictors at all four spatial scales. Output from the full-model BRT was examined to determine the scale for each predictor that had the largest relative importance in predicting abundance of each species in the point counts. The second BRT (the “selected scales model”) used just the single most important scale for each land cover, forest age, forest biomass, and swamp variable. The third BRT (the “local model”) just used the cell-level predictor for each land cover, forest age, forest biomass, and swamp variable, while the fourth, fifth, and sixth BRTs (the “GF250 model”, “GF1000 model” and “GF2000 model”) just used respectively the landscape scale predictors for each land cover, forest age, forest biomass, and swamp variable resulting from the 250, 1000, and 2000-m Gaussian filters. All BRTs also included elevation, slope, TRI, TPI, whether a point count was within 150 m of any road, and whether a point count was within 150 m of a major road (Table 4).

In addition to the 6 BRT models above, another BRT model including acid deposition exceedance was run, since Wood Thrush are less likely to breed in areas with more acid deposition, particularly at higher elevations or in areas with more forest fragmentation (Hames et al., 2002) and since areas with more acid precipitation may support reduced amounts of calcium-rich invertebrate prey required by nestlings (Graveland, 1990; Reynolds and Perrins, 2010; Ladin, 2015). To assess the potential effects of acid rain on Wood Thrush abundance, two preliminary exceedance GIS layers developed by Julian Aherne (Trent University) were used as

additional predictors in this BRT and were extracted to point counts. The two layers measure the amounts by which a *critical load* of ions associated with acid rain precipitation (NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) is exceeded within a local environment; beyond this critical load, adverse effects caused by these ions are observed within a species or species-group of interest. In the case of these exceedance layers, the critical loads of interest are the amounts at which the 5 % most sensitive tree species are harmed by excess acid precipitation (“exceedance.05”) and the 20 % most sensitive species are harmed (“exceedance.20”). The “exceedance model” contained all the predictors of the “full model” but also considered values from the “exceedance.05” and “exceedance.20” layers described above. Since exceedance data are missing for parts of the Wood Thrush’s range in Canada where the species was suspected beforehand of being more abundant and many point count surveys still were not assigned exceedance values after data extraction, fewer point count data were available to be used in the “exceedance model” than other BRT models (Figure 4, Table 4).

Figure 4. Map of point counts (blue points) available for boosted regression tree models relative to distribution of non-missing exceedance values for modelling acid rain effects on Wood Thrush. Missing exceedance values are white areas within Canadian lands.

Table 4. Description and sources of predictor variables used in boosted regression tree models of Wood Thrush abundance in Canada.

Variable	Description	Abbreviation	Citation
Land cover	Eleven land cover classes for individual Canadian provinces – Quebec, Ontario, New Brunswick, Nova Scotia - (30 m resolution) based on Landsat satellite imagery in 2011, 2015, and 2020; used to create binary land cover rasters resampled to 250 m resolution.	Land cover	AAFC 2021
Forest stand age	Local stand age since last disturbance (years) extracted from forest vegetation layers (250 m resolution) in 2001 and 2011. Stand age layer processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean stand age within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	Stand age	Beaudoin et al. 2014
Forest stand live above-ground biomass (branch, foliage, woody stem, bark, total live)	Different fractions of live above-ground biomass (tonnes per ha) extracted from forest vegetation layers (250 m resolution) in 2001 and 2011. Stand biomass layer processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean stand biomass within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	Stand biomass	Beaudoin et al. 2014
Forest stand total dead biomass	Local stand biomass (tonnes per ha) extracted from forest vegetation layers (250 m resolution) in 2001 and 2011. Stand biomass layer processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean stand biomass within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	Stand biomass	Beaudoin et al. 2014
Roadside status	Roadside150 = whether a point count was within 150 m of any roadside (1) or not (0) MajorRoad150 = whether a point count was within 150 m of a heavy traffic road (arterial road, expressway, highway, freeway, ramp, rapid transit road) (1) or not (0).	Road	CanVec 2021
Elevation	1-km elevation raster associated with the climate raster geodatabase used in geographically weighted regression models	elev	Wang et al. 2016
Topographic Position Index	The difference between the elevation of a focal cell and the mean of its 8 surrounding cells. Positive and negative values correspond to ridges and valleys, respectively, while zero values correspond generally to flat areas (except a special case where a focal cell with a value 5 can have surrounding cells with values of 4×1 and 4×9, resulting in a TPI of 0).	TPI	Amatulli et al. 2018
Terrain Ruggedness Index	The mean of the absolute differences in elevation between a focal cell and its 8 surrounding cells. It quantifies the total elevation change across the 3×3	TRI	Amatulli et al. 2018

	cells. Flat areas have a value of zero whereas mountain areas with steep ridges have positive values, which can be greater than 2000m in the Himalaya area.		
Slope	0 – 41.5 degrees	slope	Amatulli et al. 2018
Swamp – New Brunswick	Wetland shapefile filtered to swamps only, rasterized to a 30-m swamp layer, then resampled to 250 m (proportion of land within swamps locally – 150 m), then processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean proportion of land within swamps within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	swamp	New Brunswick Department of Environment and Local Government 2021
Swamp – Nova Scotia	Wetland shapefile intersected with merged Forest Inventory shapefiles from all of Nova Scotia, filtered to polygons with 25 % or greater tree cover, rasterized to a 30-m swamp layer, then resampled to 250 m (proportion of land within swamps locally – 150 m), then processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean proportion of land within swamps within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	swamp	Nova Scotia Department of Lands and Forestry 2021
Swamp - Ontario	30-m Ontario Land Cover v.2.0 raster layer resampled to 250 m (proportion of land within swamps locally – 150 m), then processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean proportion of land within swamps within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	swamp	Ontario Land Cover Compilation v.2.0 2016
Swamp - Quebec	Wetland shapefile data compiled by Ducks Unlimited from different regions in southern Quebec from 2010 – 2015. Shapefile filtered to swamps only, then rasterized to 30-m swamp layer, then resampled to 250 m (proportion of land within swamps locally – 150 m), then processed with Gaussian filtering to estimate mean proportion of land within swamps within 250, 1000, and 2000 m.	swamp	Ducks Unlimited 2015
Acid rain exceedance	Exceedance.05 = the amount by which local acid rain impacts exceed a critical load value at which 5 % of most acid-sensitive tree species are harmed. Exceedance.20 = the amount by which local acid rain impacts exceed a critical load value at which 20 % of most acid-sensitive tree species are harmed.	Exceedance.05 Exceedance.20	Julian Aherne (Trent University) 2021

The “rpart” (Therneau and Atkinson, 2019), “gbm” (Greenwell et al., 2020), and “dismo” packages (Hijmans et al., 2020) were used to construct BRTs and the raster package was used to create prediction layers of Wood Thrush abundance under each BRT. As some areas in the study area had far greater densities of point counts than other areas (Figures 3 – 4), the areas with more point counts could unduly influence results if all point count data were used in modelling. To account for spatial correlation in the data and create random sample data sets for training and

cross-validating each BRT, cross-validation (“blockCV” package [Valavi et al., 2019]) was used to partition study regions into blocks sharing overall similarity in BRT predictor values that were independent of the values in other blocks. Training and testing data were drawn evenly from the blocks. Five-fold cross-validation (Leathwick et al., 2006) was used both to select the number of trees that minimized residual deviance in the final BRT model and to evaluate predictive ability of the final BRT model (Hastie et al., 2001; Bühlmann and Yu, 2003). There were 5 initial models of 50 trees each, a tree complexity of 3, a learning rate of 0.01, and a bag fraction of 0.5 (the proportion of data in each subset used to train the model as opposed to the out-of-bag 50 % of data used to test the model). Prediction error (PE or residual deviance) was calculated for each BRT for tree sizes 1 to 3 from the “out-of-bag” data and pooled across the 5 boosted trees, then the number of trees in each model was augmented by 50 trees and the process was repeated.

Predictive ability of the 7 BRT models was compared by examining 5-fold cross validation correlation in the test data and by examining the intercept and slope values from a regression of predicted versus observed Wood Thrush abundance. Better predictive ability is indicated by higher correlation, intercepts closer to 0, and slopes closer to 1. Once a final BRT for predicting Wood Thrush abundance was selected based on its predictive accuracy, that selected BRT was rerun on 250 random sample data sets to obtain 250 rasters of predicted current Wood Thrush density and distribution (as of 2020) and 250 sets of and 250 sets of model regression trees for predicting future Wood Thrush abundance from land use simulation outputs.

Projecting Future Wood Thrush Abundance and Distribution Under Different Climate and Harvest Scenarios

The forest disturbance simulator Landis-II (Scheller & Mladenoff, 2004) (hereafter, “Landis”) was used to predict how environmental variables from the Wood Thrush BRTs might change in amount and location under different climate and land use scenarios in eastern Canada. There are two basic software components within Landis itself. First, there is a succession model (PICUS) (version 1.5; <http://picus.boku.ac.at>) describing shade tolerance, age of a tree species’ sexual maturity, dispersal distance, reproduction on-site after fire, and responses of either individual trees or cohorts of different tree species to new forest openings created by disturbances. In PICUS, different species-age cohorts occur within square 100-m² cells and these cells interact, in that propagule from sexually mature trees in one cell can disperse to and potentially colonize newly disturbed adjacent cells within dispersal distance. As simulations run, individual species’ cohorts age with each time step. The second component within Landis is a spatially explicit environment in which simulated disturbances can be added and then spread from cell to cell. This environment consists of raster layers describing different forest types and non-forest lands and zones where different disturbance types may occur. Overlaying these raster layers enables Landis to calculate if disturbance affects a given forest location or not. Together these components make Landis a forest landscape model (FLM) that has been widely used to project future forest habitat available to wildlife (e.g., Tremblay et al., 2018; Cadieux et al., 2019, 2020).

A third component outside of the basic Landis software consists of external packages (modules or extensions) that can be “plugged” into Landis to either simulate a particular type of

disturbance or produce output resulting from simulated disturbances. These packages are modular in the sense that: 1) they are not necessary for Landis to function outside of the scenarios for which the modules are built; and 2) in that the packages take inputs produced by either basic Landis or by other packages and produce outputs that may serve as inputs for other packages. Different types of disturbance can be simulated by these modules, including harvest (Gustafson et al., 2000), fire (He and Mladenoff, 1999; Perera et al., 2008; Sturtevant et al., 2009; Syphard et al., 2011), insect and pathogen outbreaks (Sturtevant et al., 2004; Foster, 2011; Tonini et al., 2018), wind events, roads (<https://github.com/Klemet>), and browsing (<https://sites.google.com/site/Landismodel/extensions/browse-disturbance>). Newer modules may simulate the same types of disturbance as older modules under a wider variety of environmental conditions: such modules may be developed so that disturbances can be modelled as a function of climate variables to predict effects of climate change (Perera et al., 2008; Sturtevant et al., 2009; Syphard et al., 2011; de Bruijn et al., 2014). Still other modules have been developed to produce a wider variety of outputs beyond presence/absence of a tree species' cohort and disturbance/non-disturbance of individual cells (e.g., biomass outputs: Syphard et al., 2011; de Bruijn et al., 2014). As the outputs from some modules serve as inputs to other modules, modules within the Landis environment communicate with each other, and some modules require the presence of specific other modules to work.

Beyond the basic Landis software and its modules, future landscape scenarios are conceived by investigators interested in projecting how forest variables change over time under a specific set of disturbances. Scenarios can be varied according to: 1) the types of disturbance modelled; 2) the probability, amount, severity, and spatial arrangement of disturbances; 3) whether specific disturbance types are affected by climate variables and if so, how those climate variables change over time; 4) whether one type of disturbance influences the probability, amount, severity, and spatial arrangement of other disturbance types; and 5) how growth rates, survival rates, succession, height and biomass of individual trees within cohorts are affected by disturbance or presence of other tree species.

Landis Simulation Setup

In eastern Canada, 200-year-long future landscape scenarios were developed, in which forest structure changed under different combinations of climate and harvest. Baseline climate scenarios assume present day levels of atmospheric CO₂, temperatures and precipitation affecting growth rates of tree species and probabilities of natural forest disturbances. Climate change scenarios assume that increases in atmospheric CO₂ due mainly to human activities occur, described by Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) values (e. g. 2.6, 4.5, and 8.5). RCP values are estimates of the change in energy flux measured in Watts/m² and increases in atmospheric CO₂ are associated with higher RCP values (Moss et al., 2010; Van Vuuren et al., 2011). In the southern boreal forest region, mean annual temperatures are predicted to rise from 3.5 °C. (RCP 2.6) to 7.5 °C. (RCP 8.5) by 2100 AD relative to 2000 AD, while average precipitation is predicted to rise by 10-25 per cent (CanESM2; Arora et al., 2011). Increasing temperatures are predicted to increase the frequency and intensity of and area affected by fires (Boulanger et al., 2014; Boulanger et al., 2016a; Stralberg et al., 2018)), drought (Michaelian et al., 2011), and outbreaks of insect pests and pathogens of tree species (Pureswaran et al., 2018)

within Canada's boreal forests. However, increases in these natural disturbances in combination with higher CO₂ concentrations are predicted to negatively affect slower-growing coniferous tree species more than the deciduous tree species used as Wood Thrush breeding habitat, leading to either younger-on-average, deciduous-dominated boreal forests or conversion of boreal forests to parkland or grassland (Mahon et al., 2014; Boulanger et al., 2016b; Stralberg et al., 2018; Mekonnen et al., 2019).

Within Landis, the current forest landscapes in each province were initialized using vegetation data derived from multiple sources, including stand age cohort data from provincial forest inventory plots, harvest data from forestry companies, private conservation research organization GIS products, and the Canadian National Forest Inventory (NFI; nfi.nfis.org). Cell resolution was set at 250 m and time steps for simulations were set at 10 years. Cells were assigned to a "land type" with homogeneous soil and climate conditions (Mansuy et al., 2014). Current climate data were generated from 30-year monthly climate normals for 1961-1990, which were interpolated from climate station records (McKenny et al., 2013). The current climate normals were merged with projected future monthly changes predicted from the Canadian Earth System Model version 2, up to 2100 AD (CanESM2; Arora et al., 2011). RCP scenarios 4.5 and 8.5 were downloaded from the World Climate Research Program (WCRP) Climate Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) archive.

A modified version of the Biomass Succession module (Scheller and Mladenoff, 2004) was used to simulate growth, succession, and mortality of tree species' cohorts in place of individual trees as done by the basic Age-Only Succession module. The Biomass Succession module enables multiple cohorts to occupy and compete for growing spaces within 100-m² forest gaps (cells) and estimates maximum biomass (maxAGB; g/m²), maximum aboveground net primary productivity (maxANPP; g m⁻² year⁻¹) and species establishment probability (SEP) from PICUS by running monospecific stand simulations for each combination of species, climate conditions and land type. Modifications are described further in Tremblay et al. (2018).

The Biomass Harvest module (Gustafson et al., 2000) was used to simulate harvest plans. Input files for this module outline management areas, individual forest stands within management areas, and a text file containing harvest prescriptions and implementations for each management area and stand. Individual harvest prescriptions rank tree species according to harvest priority and indicate minimum harvest age and what cohorts of each species to harvest. Harvest implementations list management areas, prescriptions to use in each management area, the maximum percentage of a management area that can be harvested in any time step, and the start and stop times within the simulation when harvest is allowed to occur. The Biomass Harvest module permits the simulation of partial thinning and specifying what percentage of a cohort to harvest.

The Base Fire module (He and Mladenoff, 1999) and Base Wind module (Mladenoff and He, 1999) were used to simulate fire and wind disturbances. The Ontario, Quebec, New Brunswick, and Nova Scotia study areas were divided into fire regions, or collections of cells with the same fire parameters (ignition probability, and maximum, minimum and mean fire size). The fire regions correspond to both current and future predicted Canadian Homogeneous Fire Regime

Zones (Boulanger et al., 2014). Cells within a fire region may or may not be contiguous with each other, and parameters can be updated during the simulation to account for predicted changes due to climate change. The Base Fire and Base Wind modules interact with each other so that fire spread is shaped and directed by wind speed and direction, with higher wind speeds resulting in more linear fires. Each fire event is ranked a severity rating from 1 to 5 based on the amount of fuel burned and time since the last fire. Larger severity ratings result in more or all a cohort being killed in a cell undergoing a fire event. If fire severity is a 5, 100% of a cohort is killed; otherwise, fire damage is based on the severity rating and tolerance values of each species cohort to fire. Younger cohorts generally have lower tolerance values to fire. In contrast, older cohorts have a higher probability of mortality given a wind event of certain intensity.

The Biological Disturbance Agent (BDA) (Sturtevant et al., 2004) was used to simulate the effect of spruce budworm (*Choristoneura fumiferana*) outbreaks on coniferous forests within the study areas. Probability of a spruce budworm outbreak within cells depends on: 1) tolerance or susceptibility of individual tree species and cohort to a particular BDA; 2) site resource dominance, or the amount of each tree species cohort in a cell; 3) the presence of land type modifiers or disturbance modifiers (e.g. fire, wind) that adjust site resource dominance and susceptibility in a cell; 4) and neighborhood-level factors (the amount of suitable hosts within a given number of cells around each cell, plus the ability of spruce budworm to disperse across cells with unsuitable hosts).

Landis Scenarios

For the Wood Thrush study, existing scenarios developed for other studies were used. There were three study areas within the Wood Thrush range in Canada in southern Quebec, New Brunswick, and Nova Scotia. Six scenarios were used from southern Quebec; these scenarios are described in detail in Boulanger and Puigdevall (2021). Due to its size and its data processing requirements, the Quebec study area was divided into three smaller subsections (“123est”, “345ouest”, “45est”) and the scenarios were run separately for each area. The six scenarios in Quebec consisted of combinations of three climate scenarios (baseline, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5) and two harvest scenarios (harvest vs. no new harvest) in which the harvest regime consisted of ecosystem-based forest management. Three scenarios were used from New Brunswick, consisting of a harvest scenario (1 % clear-cut per year) under three different climate scenarios (baseline, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5). For Nova Scotia, there were 9 combinations of 3 climate scenarios (baseline, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5) and 3 harvest scenarios (no new harvest, ecosystem-based forest management, historic clear-cutting rates) run. Ecosystem-based forest management assumes a maximum of 40 % of trees removed from a harvest area, a minimum forest age of 80 years prior to harvest of an unharvested area, and a minimum age of 40 years since last harvest in a previously harvested area. Clear-cutting assumes 100 % removal of trees from harvest areas with no minimum stand age prior to first harvest or since last harvest. The Nova Scotia scenarios are described in detail in an upcoming manuscript describing a completed study of projected future habitat for Canada Warbler (Denes et al. *in prep*). Besides harvest, these scenarios also simulated disturbance by fire and spruce budworm outbreaks, which varied under different climate scenarios.

Landis Outputs

Outputs from the Landis scenarios included raster layers showing how total area in different disturbance types, stand age, and tree species changed over time in 10-year increments. To reduce the influence of a specific simulation run on projected Wood Thrush numbers, each Landis scenario was run in each study area five times, resulting in a new set of raster layers. These raster outputs were then used as inputs to the 250 BRTs for Wood Thrush in each study region to get 250 prediction layers of Wood Thrush densities for each time step, scenario, and simulation run. From these prediction layers, raster layers of mean Wood Thrush density and of standard deviation in density at 250-m resolution were produced for each scenario, simulation run, and study area. Due to time constraints, the Wood Thrush study used prediction outputs from 2100 AD. As Landis only simulated change and predicted Wood Thrush density in forested areas, the output rasters were filled in using predicted Wood Thrush density mean and standard deviation for non-forested areas from a current density layer. Density predictions > 1 male/ha (<<< 1 % of pixels in all Landis study areas) were reset to 1 male/ha before generating population estimates and identifying Landis outputs to use in conservation planning. This threshold value was used based on reported densities of Wood Thrush in the literature (Gauthier and Aubry, 1995; Evans et al., 2020).

Calculating Trends for Landis Scenarios and Comparing to Breeding Bird Survey Trends

The current population of Wood Thrush was estimated in the parts of each study area that were subject to Landis simulations, by generating 250 prediction layers of current Wood Thrush density in each study area, then calculating mean and standard deviation from those predictions in each location (250-m pixel). The five mean density layers from each Landis scenario in each time step were used to obtain a population estimate in 2100 A. D. for the Wood Thrush's range in Quebec, New Brunswick, and Nova Scotia. The five mean density layers from each Landis scenario in each time step were used to obtain a population estimate in 2050 A. D. and 2100 A. D. for the Wood Thrush's range in each province, starting with Quebec and Nova Scotia. Population estimates were made after adjusting unusually high density estimates to a threshold of 1 male/ha based on density observations for Wood Thrush in the literature (Gauthier and Aubry, 1995; Evans et al., 2020).

Finally, a best-case (most + or least – trend), medium-case (median trend), and worst-case (least + or most – trend) scenario was identified for each study area, measuring the percent difference between the current population and each scenario population in 2100 A. D. The mean and standard deviation density layers for these scenarios in 2100 A. D. were set aside for conservation planning exercises in Zonation software.

Stage 3b. Population Risk Assessment: Regional Models of Wood Thrush Abundance for ALCES Online Scenarios

In most of the Wood Thrush's range within Canada (southern Ontario, southern Quebec, New Brunswick, Nova Scotia), the forest succession simulator Landis can be used to simulate multiple disturbances (harvest, pest and pathogen outbreaks, fire, wind damage) and

environmental variables (e. g. climate variables) that either set back forest succession or affect growth rates of individual tree species. Landis can track changes in forest cover that affect habitat for forest-dwelling species like Wood Thrush, and in turn Wood Thrush abundance and distribution can be projected over time. In southern Ontario however – particularly the Great Lakes / St. Lawrence Plain BCR, the regions where Wood Thrush populations are concentrated currently lack data that can be used to model how individual tree species respond to climate and other environmental variables. Thus, Landis cannot currently project changes in Wood Thrush habitat over time in most of southern Ontario, although portions of the Wood Thrush’s Ontario range within the Boreal Hardwood Transition and Boreal Softwood Shield BCRs do have Landis coverage.

In contrast to Landis, another land use simulator called ALCES Online (<https://www.online.alces.ca/>) currently has coverage for the whole province of Ontario. Unlike Landis, ALCES Online cannot simulate changes in individual tree species biomass like Landis; however, ALCES Online can be used to model a wide variety of disturbance types and patterns and users can specify conditions informing when, where, and how much of a specific disturbance occurs (Carlson et al., 2014; Carlson and Stelfox, 2014; Carlson et al., 2019; Leston et al., 2020). Simulated disturbances are not limited to forests in ALCES Online, so this simulator may be useful in the future for projecting habitat change for non-forest-dwelling species of concern to the Canadian Wildlife Service.

In addition to being able to project habitat for Wood Thrush in the parts of its Canadian range without Landis coverage, there is interest in comparing how similar or different predictions over time are between the two simulators. Comparisons can be made by first generating scenario projections across the whole Wood Thrush range in Ontario, then clipping the predicted Wood Thrush distribution at each scenario and time step to the parts of the Wood Thrush range in Ontario that are covered by Landis.

Boosted Regression Tree (BRT) Models for Wood Thrush Used with ALCES Online

The final BRT model that was selected for predicting Wood Thrush abundance from Landis outputs was modified in two ways to predict Wood Thrush abundance from ALCES Online outputs. First, while the final BRT model used for Landis predictions used 20 predictor variables including total live aboveground biomass of all tree species (Table 4), the BRT model used for ALCES Online predictions contained the same predictor variables except for total live aboveground biomass, since that variable cannot currently be modeled within ALCES Online. Second, as ALCES Online currently can simulate environmental variables at several resolutions but not at 250-m resolution, the predictor variables used in the BRT were resampled to 200-m resolution (the closest available resolution in ALCES Online to 250 m), prior to running the BRT (*ALCES 200*) that would be used for making predictions from ALCES Online outputs. To determine how the change in resolution might affect predictions, a version of this BRT was run with the same 19 predictors, where the predictor data were still at the original 250-m resolution (*ALCES 250*), and outputs from the two BRTs were compared to each other.

The same point count data that were available for the final BRT used with Landis (Table 3) were potentially available for the *ALCES 200* and *ALCES 250* BRTs, meaning that while

ALCES Online simulations were only run in Ontario, point counts from the Wood Thrush range in Quebec, New Brunswick and Nova Scotia were used in the *ALCES 200* and *ALCES 250* BRTs.

Projecting Future Wood Thrush Abundance and Distribution in ALCES Online

ALCES Online Simulation Setup

ALCES Online came preloaded with multiple shapefile and raster layers clipped to the extent of Ontario or to smaller extents. Raster layers are stored as indicators in ALCES Online, in which values can vary among adjacent pixels. Indicators include but are not limited to summarized natural land cover types, human footprint types, and climate variables. There are layers for detailed land cover types limited to southern Ontario, based on the SOLRIS Landsat-derived data layer product. These layers are available in and can be analyzed at different resolutions (100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000, 10000, 25000 m). The resolutions available for visualizing in ALCES Online maps depend on the size of the study area, with finer-scale resolutions only available for simulation, output visualization, and output downloading in smaller study areas. Natural land cover and human footprint layers stored in the folders OMNR Detailed Footprint, OMNR Summarized Footprint, OMNR Summarized Land Cover, SOLRIS Detailed Land Cover are expressed in percentage values, i.e. the percentage of each pixel covered by a specific footprint or land cover type. Each of these folders is described as a unity layer, because the percentages of each footprint or land cover type within a unity layer add up to 100 % or a proportion of 1.0 in each pixel. Most of the land cover types in which changes over time were simulated (*Dense Decid ON*, *Dense Mixed ON*, *Dense Conif ON*, *Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON*) were in the OMNR Summarized Land Cover folder, but in the SOLRIS Detailed Land Cover folder, *Plantations – Trees Cultivated* layer was used when simulating harvest within woodlots. Another forest layer in the OMNR Summarized Land Cover folder - *Treed Wetland ON* – was assumed to remain constant and unharvested in the simulations, as were non-forest layers in the OMNR Summarized Land Cover and Footprint folders.

Shapefile layers including those for different jurisdictions (e.g., Forest Management Units, parks, First Nations reserves, etc.) are stored as regions within ALCES Online. Regions are used to define the study area in which simulations occur and indicators are visualized. Regions or individual polygons within those regions can be also used for filtering simulated disturbance actions based on location within the study area rather than a specific pixel value of a pre-loaded or derived indicator.

Some indicator layers necessary for tracking land use change and modelling Wood Thrush habitat and populations after simulation do not come pre-loaded in ALCES Online and cannot be derived from existing pre-loaded indicators. Therefore, these indicator layers were imported as raster layers into ALCES Online Data Library. A forest age raster layer (as of 2020: year 0 of the ALCES Online scenarios) was created at 200-m resolution in the program R, using multiple data sources. First, the satellite-based forest stand layer with estimates from 2011, used in the BRTs (Beaudoin et al., 2014) was resampled to 200-m resolution and used to estimate mean stand age as of 2011. Second, the default stand age as of 2020 was calculated by adding 9

to the stand age value for each pixel. Third, harvest shapefile data (Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources' Forest Research Institute, 2021) were used to estimate stand age within cut-blocks as of 2020. Similarly, insect outbreak and fire shapefile data (Ontario Forest Resource Inventory, 2021) were used to estimate stand age as of 2020 within outbreak areas described as tree mortality events and within burns. Fourth, raster layers for recent harvest, insect outbreaks, and fires were created with the same extent, resolution, and projection as the default stand age layer. Fifth, Landsat-derived Agriculture Canada land cover layers for Ontario in 2020 (AAFC, 2021) were used to create a Landsat total forests 2020 layer, to account for other areas where forests were replaced by non-forestry land uses. Finally, all layers were combined in one raster stack, and stand age within the recent harvest, fire and insect outbreak layers was to correct the default stand age of pixels located within the rasterized recent harvest, burn and outbreak locations. Default stand age was reset to 0 for any pixels in which Landsat total forests = 0; otherwise, the minimum stand age within completely non-forested areas would be 9.

Additional shapefiles were uploaded into ALCES Online to serve as the boundaries for running a scenario in different parts of the Wood Thrush's range in Ontario, since the entire range of the Wood Thrush in Ontario was too large to run scenarios at 200-m resolution. One shapefile consisted of the intersection of the Wood Thrush's range with Ontario's Forest Management Units, in which forestry occurs on Crown lands. The other shapefile consisted of the intersection of the Wood Thrush's range in Ontario with Bird Conservation Regions 8 ("Boreal Softwood Shield"), 12 ("Boreal Hardwood Transition"), and 13 ("Great Lakes / St. Lawrence Plain"). Most of Bird Conservation Region 13 is dominated by urban and agricultural landscapes outside of Forest Management Units, where most forestry occurs on private woodlots. The two shapefiles permitted scenarios to be run separately by Forest Management Unit or by Bird Conservation Region. The extent of different harvest types (clear-cut, shelterwood forestry, selective logging on Crown land, selective logging on private woodlots) varies greatly among BCRs and FMUs. All the Wood Thrush's range within BCRs 8 and 13 occurs within FMUs, where there is GIS data available for simulating appropriate amounts of forest harvest and other disturbances.

Harvest on Crown lands was estimated from GIS data for Forest Management Units from the Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources' Forest Research Institute (OMNDMNR, 2021). In ArcGIS, separate shapefiles were compiled for clear-cut, shelterwood, and selective logging polygons representing cutblocks harvested from 1990 – 2019, then intersected with an FMU boundary shapefile clipped to the Wood Thrush's range in Ontario. The attribute table of each intersection was exported and in R, the harvest polygons were filtered to those harvested from 2010-2019. Total decadal harvest area, mean harvest size, and maximum harvest polygon size were summarized separately for each FMU and each BCR for each harvest type (clear-cutting, shelterwood, selective logging) (dplyr package v. 1.0.5 [Wickam et al., 2021]). Histograms were generated to obtain approximate size class distributions for harvest polygons by harvest type and BCR; however, as most scenarios were ultimately run separately for each FMU and due to the large number of FMUs, mean harvest size and total area disturbed per decade were used rather than a size class distribution to model disturbances in each FMU, to make analyses more reproducible.

Clear-cutting from 2010-2019 was commonplace in FMUs in both BCR 8 (43 %) and BCR 12 (57 %) but was negligible (~0%) on FMUs within BCR 13. Simulated clear-cuts were assumed to remove up to 90 % of trees (36,000 m²) of a fully forested 200-m pixel, reset mean stand age to 10 years (since on-site shrubs and saplings up to 10 years old would remain), and be conducted in pixels with a minimum stand age of 60 years where tree cover (*Dense Conif ON + Dense Decid ON + Sparse / Undifferentiated Forest ON*) was 50 % or more. Simulated clear-cuts did not occur in forested wetlands or mixed-wood forests. Clear-cutting is often recommended for boreal coniferous trees and some faster-growing, shade-intolerant deciduous trees (e. g. aspen, poplar), so would be likelier to be practiced in stands classified as coniferous or deciduous but not mixed-wood.

Shelterwood harvesting was virtually confined to FMUs within BCR 12. Simulated shelterwood harvest was assumed to remove up to 50 % trees (20,000 m²) within a fully forested pixel, reset mean stand age to 20 years due to the presence of remaining overstory trees, and be conducted in pixels with a minimum stand age of 60 years where tree cover (*Dense Decid ON + Dense Mixed ON*) was 50 % or more.

Selective logging on Crown Lands was virtually confined to FMUs within BCR 12, although harvest in private woodlots in BCR 13 is primarily via selective logging. Simulated selective harvest was assumed to remove a maximum of 10 % trees (10,000 m²) within a fully forested pixel, reset mean stand age to 60 years, and be conducted in pixels with a minimum stand age of 80 years where tree cover (*Dense Decid ON*) was 50 % or more: removal of trees by selective logging reduced average stand age but that keeping many older trees standing kept the average stand age well above 0.

In contrast to the FMUs, GIS-based harvest data were not available for most lands within BCR 13, where harvest within woodlots was simulated based on summary data within reports. Harvest within private woodlots in southern Ontario was estimated using data from Kim (2020). Due to the overlap between the study area in Kim (2020) and BCR 13, the simulation of woodlot harvest was confined to this BCR and just within the parts of the BCR outside of FMUs. In contrast to the FMUs, size class distributions were used to set harvest within BCR 13 because there were existing estimates of proportion of total harvest area per decade (543,100 ha: diameter-limited cutting and good forestry practices methods combined) in different forest types (coniferous [18 %], deciduous [46 %], mixed-wood [21 %], plantations [7 %]). Separate harvest allocations were modelled for woodlots to maintain these proportions among future harvests in the baseline scenario. A size class distribution for woodlots was obtained from Watkins (2011): 0-10 ha (95.6 %), 10-99 ha (4.2 %), 100+ ha (0.2 %) and was used for each forest type. Selective forestry was used to maintain woodlots while harvesting, with up to a maximum of 10 % of a stand being removed by selective logging, stand age reset to 60 years, and a minimum stand age of 80 years for harvest to occur.

Spruce budworm (*Choristoneura fumiferana*) outbreaks were simulated using GIS data in the Ontario Forest Resource Inventory (FRI) from the Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources' Forest Research Institute (Ontario Forest Resource Inventory, 2021). In ArcGIS, a shapefile with insect outbreak polygons for different species from 1990 – 2020 was intersected with both a

FMU shapefile clipped to the Wood Thrush's Ontario range and a BCR shapefile clipped to the Wood Thrush's Ontario range. Information contained in the shapefile included outbreak severity: we treated events described as a "Mortality" as removal of sufficient numbers of live trees to reset forest succession to 0. The attribute tables from each intersected shapefile were exported and summaries were generated for each BCR and FMU for total area of tree mortality attributed to spruce budworm (2011-2020), mean outbreak area, and maximum outbreak size. As with the harvest shapefile output within FMUs, histograms were generated to obtain approximate size class distributions for spruce budworm outbreaks causing tree mortality for each BCR and FMU; however, as most scenarios were ultimately run separately for each FMU and due to the large number of FMUs, mean outbreak size and total area disturbed per decade were used rather than a size class distribution to model disturbances in each FMU, to make analyses more reproducible. In contrast, the size class distribution for budworm outbreaks in BCR 13 was used to simulate these outbreaks in BCR 13.

Budworm outbreaks causing tree mortality were present in all 3 BCRs, with a total area of 73,917 ha (73 % in Boreal Hardwood Transition, 23 % in Great Lakes/St. Lawrence, 4 % in Boreal Softwood Shield) from 2011-2020. In the Boreal Hardwood Transition BCR, 90 % of mortality-causing budworm outbreaks were 0-50 ha, 7.5 % were 50-150 ha, and 2.5 % were larger. In the Boreal Softwood Shield BCR, 85 % of mortality-causing budworm outbreaks were 0-15 ha, 13 % were 15-45 ha, and 2 % were larger. In the Great Lakes/St. Lawrence BCR, 83 % of mortality-causing budworm outbreaks were 0-37.5 ha, 13 % were 37.5-112.5 ha, 3 % were 112.5-185 ha, and 1 % were larger. I assumed that budworm outbreaks were assumed to only occur in stands where coniferous host trees were present, i. e. coniferous forests > 50 %, reset stand age to 20 years, and that trees needed to be 60 years old before becoming infested.

Apart from temporary disturbances like harvest and budworm outbreaks, the only other disturbance that was used to reset forest age was fire, within three of the FMUs (Boundary Waters Forest, Missinaibi Forest, Pic Forest) where there were no recent harvest or budworm disturbances according to the GIS data. Fire was not considered to be a significant disturbance within the Landis coverage in the Wood Thrush's Ontario range (Chao, 2011) but was simulated in the Boundary Waters Forest, Missinaibi Forest, and Pic Forest FMUs so that forest age did not invariably and unrealistically increase in those FMUs throughout the scenario runs. Fire data was obtained and summarized by FMU in a similar way to budworm outbreak data, by intersecting shapefile data for recent fire disturbances (Ontario Forest Resource Inventory, 2021) with an FMU shapefile clipped to the Wood Thrush's Ontario range. In the exported attribute table of this intersected shapefile, the year of a given fire disturbance was used to filter to the most recent 10 years of fire, after which total decadal burn, mean burn size and maximum burn size were summarized for each FMU.

While some forest is permanently converted to other habitats by urban or agricultural land (631 ha/year) and permanent roads (470 ha/year) (<https://www.ontario.ca/page/deforestation>), permanent habitat conversion was not simulated in ALCES Online, to make ALCES Online scenarios more comparable to Landis scenarios. Unlike Landis, simulations in ALCES Online cannot be run for more than 50 years at the current time.

Thus, there is not as much time to observe large effects of climate change in ALCES Online as in Landis. However, some disturbances that are projected to increase with global warming (e. g. fire, insect outbreaks) could be modelled within other scenarios by increasing the decadal amount of those disturbances, either evenly or increasing over time.

ALCES Online Scenario

A single baseline scenario was run separately for each FMU within the Wood Thrush's Ontario range and for BCR 13. The scenarios were stored in the "WOTH 200" project in the ALCES Online Mapper component. The baseline scenario was replicated and run five times in each FMU and in BCR 13 to obtain separate outputs. Resolution was set to 200 m, and simulation and output time steps were set to decades rather than years, starting from 2010 and ending in 2060. Note: "2010" is treated as Year 0 and simulations run for 50 simulation-years, even though the data for Year 0 is from 2020. As such, simulations project land use from 2020 to 2070. The baseline scenario is a forecast of future land use as opposed to a hindcast or natural range of variation scenario, and the "Ontario CWS" user group has access to scenario results (Appendix I).

Multiple pre-disturbance indicator variables (*Forest Origin ON* = Cut, Fire, Pest) were selected whose values were tracked over the course of simulation when a given scenario was run. As these pre-disturbance indicators are associated with the "WOTH 200" project, they will be tracked when any scenario within that project is run. The indicators were associated with variables used within Wood Thrush abundance models and included both pre-loaded indicators in ALCES Online and imported derived indicators like forest age (Appendix I).

Within each baseline scenario run in each FMU and BCR 13, there were separate, multiple actions, which are different types of simulated disturbances like harvest, fire, insect outbreaks, or human footprint. Actions can be specified as temporary disturbances or permanent changes in land cover: currently, the baseline scenario is only modelling temporary disturbances (harvest, spruce budworm outbreaks). Forest habitat is assumed to only be set back in age and disturbances are assumed to not change the pre-existing forest type. A given type of disturbance can have one or more actions associated with it. For example, the indicator "Harvest" has separate actions for clear-cut, shelterwood, and selective logging within FMUs and logging within private woodlots in BCR 13. Separate actions were created for each harvest type in the FMUs because there was enough data to simulate each harvest type separately (area disturbed, distribution of disturbance size classes, in what forest type and at what forest stand age and where in Ontario the harvest type should occur). In contrast, a single harvest action was used in BCR 13 for woodlot harvest (Appendix I).

Since there was enough information to do so, each disturbance action was specified as "standard" or "scheduled", i.e., the amount of that disturbance to simulate was specified each type step, as opposed to being based on "natural dynamics" (triggered by a condition, in which case the disturbance may or may not occur at all in a given time step or the amount is completely dependent on other conditions), and all disturbance actions in the baseline were added to the landscape rather than subtracted. An example of an action being subtracted and/or based on natural dynamics could include a logging road or seismic line after a certain amount of time (e.g.

age since construction > 20 years). Each disturbance action was assigned a schedule indicator (different from the pre-loaded and derived indicator layers) that tracks the area amount and location of the disturbance action during the simulation. For clear-cutting, shelterwood, selective logging, and woodlots, the schedule indicator was “harvest” with forest origin set to “cut” while for fire and spruce budworm outbreaks, it is “fire” (with forest origin respectively reset to “burn” or “pest”) (Appendix I).

Since all disturbances were assumed to be temporary, actions were described as “IsYield” = “yes” and “recurring” (recalculated at the start of each new decadal time step), as opposed to “Cumulative” or only calculated at the end of the simulation. Thus, there were estimates of each disturbance action for each decade. Transitions were specified in other variables caused by each disturbance action. Since harvest and outbreaks are only simulated as removing trees but allow forests to grow back, the relevant transitions were the resetting back forest age (to what age depends on the harvest type) and changing forest origin (to “cut” after harvest, to “pest” after a spruce budworm outbreak, to “fire” after fire). The age to which forests are reset depends on the harvest type: 0 for fire, 10 for clear-cutting, 20 for shelterwood or spruce budworm mortality, 60 for selective logging (Appendix I).

For each disturbance action, one or more disturbance allocations were set up, telling ALCES Online the size or size class distribution of that disturbance to simulate (in m²), how that disturbance is propagated in the landscape (e.g. random, clustered, linear), the maximum amount of a 200-m pixel (in m²) that can be affected by a disturbance, and any pixel conditions that determine whether a disturbance occurs in a pixel. A single allocation based on mean disturbance size was used for harvest, fire, and budworm outbreak actions in the FMUs due to the number of FMUs. Usually, mean disturbance size was greater than a 200-m pixel so a clustered allocation was used. When mean disturbance size was smaller than a 200-m pixel, a random allocation was used for that disturbance action in a few FMUs. In contrast to the FMUs, I used a size class distribution when simulating harvest and budworm outbreaks in BCR 13 (Appendix I).

There are parts of the study area where a disturbance action should not be simulated. For example, some kinds of harvest are negligible or not present in certain FMUs or BCR 13, so they would not be simulated as actions in those areas. Some actions will only be likely to occur in certain kinds of forest (e.g., spruce budworm outbreaks in coniferous forest) or within forests of a minimum stand age (e.g. 60 years old for clear-cuts and shelterwood logging, 80 years old for selective logging). Some actions (e.g., fire in three of the FMUs) may vary in probability of occurrence (e.g., higher probability as % conifer or forest age increases). Raster masks (dynamic rather than static since the conditions in some pixels change over the simulation) were used to specify the criteria for which a given pixel can harbour a particular disturbance. Number values in the mask are related to the relative priority that pixel gets for receiving a particular allocation and disturbance action, with 0's indicating no allocation or action assigned. Separate conditions are multiplied with one another: only pixels that satisfy all conditions (final value not equal to 0) can receive a disturbance action (Appendix I).

Within BCR 13, disturbances were only simulated in the portion occurring outside of FMUs, since disturbances were already accounted for when running the baseline scenario in

those FMUs. To specify the region where an action can occur, the other conditions were multiplied by a “1” for the whole BCR 13 region, which was then edited with regional modifiers for each FMU that partially occurred in BCR 13 (in which pixels inside those FMUs are reassigned a value of “0” (Appendix I).

Eligible indicators are those layers for which a given disturbance action can occur. For example, shelterwood logging can be applied to deciduous forests (*Dense Decid ON*) or mixed-wood forests (*Dense Mixed ON*), so these three layers are the eligible indicators for that action. In contrast, mixed-wood forests are not a suitable eligible indicator for clear-cutting or selective logging and only pixels with > 50 % of land in coniferous forest would be a suitable eligible indicator for spruce budworm outbreaks (Appendix I).

Finally, if the disturbance is a “Standard” action type, the area disturbed per decade is listed in the Schedule for each action (Appendix I).

To account for uncertainty due to simulated events, the scenario was rerun 5 times as with the Landis scenarios, with a separate set of Wood Thrush predictions generated for each simulation run (Appendix I).

ALCES Online Outputs

Once the baseline scenario was run within all FMUs and BCR 13, the raster layers were downloaded from the OMNR Summarized Land Cover and Footprint folders in Year 0, and from the Forest Age 2020 layers for each time step and simulation run. The forest layers (*Dense Decid ON*, *Dense Mixed ON*, *Dense Conif ON*, *Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON*, *Treed Wetland ON*) were used to calculate the percentage of land in each 200-m pixel that was any kind of forest, then reclassified total forest within a pixel as shrubland if the forest age < 20 years old since last disturbance. Shrubland amount was set to 0 if forest age \geq 20 years old. For each of the five forest layers we downloaded, forest amount within a pixel was set to 0 if forest age was < 20 years old for a given time step and simulation run or left unchanged if forest age \geq 20 years old. The reclassified shrubland and forest layers and non-forest layers in the OMNR Summarized Land Cover and Footprint folders were then used to generate the derived indicator layers for variables that were actually used as model predictors of Wood Thrush abundance in the ALCES Online BRT: *Structure_Stand_Age 2000 m* (from *Forest Age 2020* in a given time step), *Shrubland 2000 m* (from the *Shrubland* variable created in a given time step); *Deciduous 150 m*, *Swamp 150 m* (from *Treed Wetland ON*), *Mixedwood 2000 m*, and *Coniferous 2000 m* (from the forest variables created in a given time step); *Cult 2000 m* (from *Agriculture ON*), *Grassland 2000 m* (from *Grassland ON*), *Urban 2000 m* (from *Settlement and Infrastructure ON + Airport ON*), *Wetland 2000 m* (from *Open Wetland ON + Treed Wetland ON*), *Water 2000 m* (from *Water Anthropogenic ON + Water Natural ON*), *Barren 2000 m* (from *Alvar ON + Rock ON + Sand and Gravel ON*), *MajorRoad150* (from *Road Primary ON*), *Roadside150* (from *Road Primary ON + Road Secondary / AllSeason ON + Road Tertiary/Resource ON + Road Winter ON + Railway ON*), and *Orchard 2000 m* (a 200-m uniform raster with zero values and zero relative influence on BRT results). When summing land cover types to create derived indicators, it is recommended to only add together land covers from the same unity layer, even if those cover types exist in another layer. Because plantations are found in a different unity layer from

the OMNR Summarized Land Cover folder, plantations were not included when estimating total forest cover, prior to calculating total shrubland.

Derived indicators such as the ones mentioned above can also be created within the Advanced Calculator component of ALCES Online, using a moving window analysis function. However, it was faster to download the original Year 0 land cover layers and forest age rasters from ALCES Online and complete the data processing in R. First, for a given land cover predictor or forest age layer, the rasters from each FMU and BCR 13 were assigned a common origin (0,0) and were stitched together using the mosaic function (raster package), clipping out the parts of BCR 13 raster that occurred within one of the FMUs. Second, once raster layers were generated for each variable across the Wood Thrush's Ontario range, raster overlay analysis was used to calculate total forest cover, convert land cover values (per-cent) to the proportion values used in BRT models, and create a shrubland variable (< 20 years old) and forest (≥ 20 years old) variables at each time step. Third, for pixels where there was no wooded cover at all, forest age was reset to zero, since forest age was increased in both wooded and non-wooded pixels when scenarios were run. Fourth, moving window analyses were performed to obtain average land cover and forest age values at the spatial scales used in BRT models. These moving analyses were the same as the ones described for generating predictor data for point counts prior to BRT modelling. Finally, the rasters were stacked together, with one raster stack per time step and simulation run. The raster stacks were used with the 250 BRT resample runs to create 250 Wood Thrush prediction layers for each ALCES Online time step and simulation run. Mean and standard deviation layers of predicted density were produced for each year (2020, 2070), simulation run, and subregion (BCR 12, BCR 13). As with the Landis scenarios, density predictions > 1 male/ha (<<< 1 % of pixels in both ALCES Online study areas) were reset to 1 male/ha before generating mean density raster layers to use in conservation planning, based on Gauthier and Aubry (1995) and Evans et al. (2020).

Stage 4. Conservation Planning Scenarios to Identify the Best Present and Future Habitat for Wood Thrush

The conservation planning software Zonation 4.0 (Moilanen et al., 2009) was used to prioritize and visualize locations of the best current and future habitats to be conserved or managed for Wood Thrush in eastern Canada, based on known past locations and current and future predicted densities of Wood Thrush from the Landis scenarios, along with prediction uncertainties.

There were four Zonation scenarios for Wood Thrush in each province where there was Landis output and two Zonation scenarios for Wood Thrush in the ALCES Online baseline scenario region. All scenarios included a set of known Wood Thrush occurrence locations in each province, the current predicted mean density layer for Wood Thrush in each province from the 250 BRT bootstraps (#males/ha; 250-m resolution), and an uncertainty layer (standard deviation in predicted densities from the bootstraps from the same area), used in distribution discounting (Moilanen and Wintle 2006; Moilanen et al., 2006). All scenarios used the Core

Area Zonation cell-removal method to iteratively assign relative values to cells that increased with mean density and decreased with increasing prediction uncertainty, then removed the least valuable cells in each iteration. Higher values were assigned cells in each iteration if they were close to other cells with high Wood Thrush densities, aggregating cells together through distributive smoothing (Moilanen et al., 2014), using $\alpha=0.0057$ based on a natal dispersal distance of 70 km for Wood Thrush (Tittler et al., 2006).

The first Zonation exercise in each Landis study area consisted of only the current population distribution in each province; thus, sites were prioritized solely on where Wood Thrush was predicted to be most abundant with the lowest uncertainty. The other three Zonation exercises used in each study area also included a prediction layer and the uncertainty layer for that prediction layer for Wood Thrush distribution in 2100 A. D. from one of three Landis scenarios: a best-case scenario where the predicted future population was highest; a worst-case scenario where the predicted future population was lowest; and a medium-case scenario where the predicted future population was lower than half of the scenarios and greater than in the other half of the scenarios. The second Zonation exercise in Bird Conservation Regions 12 and 13 in Ontario used a prediction layer and associated uncertainty layer from the ALCES Online baseline scenario in 2070 A. D.

For each scenario, maps were generated that assigned locations values according to their relative value as habitat for Wood Thrush. Run-time data from each scenario were examined to determine what proportion of the current 2020 population of Wood Thrush remained as pixels in the study area were “removed” from the landscape. Custom maps and run-time plots were then generated showing the amount and location of lands to conserve up to 25, 50, 75, and 100 % of the current population. These latter maps enable estimation of the conservation-efficiency of each Zonation scenario.

Results

Management Units Identified from Geographically Weighted (GW) Models and Cluster Analysis

In the analysis of the sample data sets, BIC values increased with cluster size, but there was little increase in BIC values beyond 3 or 5 clusters, depending on the sample data set and model describing how the components (clusters) are distributed in ordinal space. The model with the highest BIC in cluster analyses of each sample data set and all sample data sets combined (“VVV”) implies that the components are ellipsoidal with varying volume, shape, and orientation (Figures 5-7). The number of identified clusters varied among sample data sets, suggesting that Wood Thrush did not consistently separate out into the same regions where it responded differently to the environment than in other parts of eastern Canada and the northeastern United States (Figures 5-7). When the maximum number of clusters was varied from 2 to 9 across all sample data combined, no region defined by cluster ID consistently separated out from others (Figure 8).

Whether 3, 5, or 7 clusters were used, the main differences in response to environmental predictors among clusters were for land cover class and roadsides rather than elevation, tree cover, or forest height. Effect size of elevation, tree cover, and forest height were negligible or slightly positive across all clusters. Effect sizes were negative for all land cover classes, probably because the GW models lacked a y-intercept. The deciduous forest category had the least negative effect of all land cover classes, probably because it represented preferred habitat for Wood Thrush. For a given number of clusters, the overlap (or lack thereof) in Wood Thrush response to individual environmental variables was not consistent across sample data sets. This result – consistent with the mapped cluster boundaries for different sample data sets – suggests that Wood Thrush did not respond differently to environmental variables in different parts of its Canadian and northeastern United States range. Thus, GW model results did not demonstrate a strong biological justification for managing Wood Thrush or modelling population risk differently across its range in Canada, although there may still be jurisdictional reasons for doing so (Figures 9 – 17).

Figure 5. Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) values estimated for cluster analyses (1-3 clusters) of effect sizes from geographically weighted regression models of Wood Thrush abundance in eastern Canada and the United States. Higher BIC values indicated that a 3-cluster solution was more probable for each sample data set than 2 clusters or a single group.

Figure 6. Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) values estimated for cluster analyses (1-5 clusters) of effect sizes from geographically weighted regression models of Wood Thrush abundance in eastern Canada and the United States. Higher BIC values indicated that a 5-cluster solution was more probable for most but not all sample data sets than 4 or fewer clusters.

Figure 7. Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) values estimated for cluster analyses (1-7 clusters) of effect sizes from geographically weighted regression models of Wood Thrush abundance in eastern Canada and the United States. Higher BIC values indicated that a 7-cluster solution was more probable for most but not all sample data sets than 6 or fewer clusters.

Figure 8. Assignment of sample data set point count locations to one of 2 to 9 clusters based on predicted response of Wood Thrush to environmental variables at each location. Point counts assigned to the same cluster due to similar predicted Wood Thrush responses have the same colour within each plot. As locations assigned to the same cluster are located closer together in space than to point counts assigned to a different cluster, it shows that a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different parts of the species' range. There may be a biological basis for this response (i.e., a species actually uses different habitats in different parts of its range) or the response may be due to differences among regions in measurement accuracy or how environmental variables are measured; however, cluster boundaries changed as the maximum number of clusters changed, suggesting that no clusters within the Wood Thrush study area consistently separated out from other clusters.

Figure 9. Assignment of point count locations in each of 10 sample data sets to 3 clusters based on predicted response of Wood Thrush to environmental variables at each location. Point counts assigned to the same cluster based on similar Wood Thrush responses have the same colour within each plot. As locations assigned to the same cluster are located closer together in space than to point counts assigned to a different cluster, it shows that a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different parts of the species' range. However, across different sample data sets, the boundaries of different clusters do not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 10. Assignment of point count locations in each of 10 sample data sets to 5 clusters based on predicted response of Wood Thrush to environmental variables at each location. Point counts assigned to the same cluster due to similar Wood Thrush responses have the same colour within each plot. As locations assigned to the same cluster are located closer together in space than to point counts assigned to a different cluster, it shows that a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different parts of the species' range. Clusters in each sample dataset suggest that Wood Thrush responds differently to the 10 predictors in southeastern Ontario versus the United States in all sample datasets and differently in southeastern Ontario from Quebec and the Maritimes in 8 out of 10 datasets. Note: for some individual datasets, a 3-cluster solution was favoured over a 5-cluster solution. However, across different sample data sets, the boundaries of different clusters do not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 11. Assignment of point count locations in each of 10 sample data sets to 7 clusters based on predicted response of Wood Thrush to environmental variables at each location. Point counts assigned to the same cluster due to similar Wood Thrush responses have the same colour within each plot. As locations assigned to the same cluster are located closer together in space than to point counts assigned to a different cluster, it shows that a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different parts of the species' range. Clusters in each sample dataset suggest that Wood Thrush responds differently to the 10 predictors in southeastern Ontario versus the United States in all sample datasets and differently in southeastern Ontario from Quebec and the Maritimes in 6 out of 10 datasets. Note: for some individual datasets, a smaller number of clusters was favoured over a 7-cluster solution. However, across different sample data sets, the boundaries of different clusters do not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 12. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are showing for 3-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets. Southeastern Ontario corresponds to cluster 2 in sample datasets 1 and 3 and to cluster 3 in the other sample datasets. The United States corresponds to cluster 1 and 3 in sample datasets 3 and to clusters 1 and 2 in other datasets. Geographically weighted regression model coefficients for all modeled land cover types are negative because the models did not include a y intercept, but the deciduous land cover type (i.e. Wood Thrush habitat) is least negative on average among land cover classes. Responses to land cover type were more negative in cluster 3 (southeastern Ontario) than clusters 1 and 2 (United States), probably because on average Wood Thrush numbers were greater in the United States. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 13. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are shown for 3-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets, after removing land cover categorical predictors. Southeastern Ontario corresponds to cluster 2 in sample datasets 1 and 3 and to cluster 3 in the other sample datasets. The United States corresponds to cluster 1 and 3 in sample datasets 3 and to clusters 1 and 2 in other datasets. Wood Thrushes in different clusters did not show significantly different responses to tree cover, forest height, or elevation, but Wood Thrushes in cluster 3 (southeastern Ontario) showed a more negative response to roadsides than in other clusters. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 14. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are shown for 5-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets, after removing land cover categorical predictors. Southeastern Ontario generally corresponds to higher cluster numbers in sample datasets. Note that for some sample datasets, a 3-cluster solution was favoured over a 5-cluster solution. The United States generally corresponds to lower cluster numbers in sample datasets. Geographically weighted regression model coefficients for all modeled land cover types are negative because the models did not include a y intercept, but the deciduous land cover type (i.e. Wood Thrush habitat) is least negative on average among land cover classes. Responses to land cover type were more negative for larger cluster numbers (southeastern Ontario) than lower cluster numbers (United States), probably because on average Wood Thrush numbers were greater in the United States. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 15. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are shown for 5-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets, after removing land cover categorical predictors. Southeastern Ontario generally corresponds to higher cluster numbers in sample datasets. Note that for some sample datasets, a 3-cluster solution was favoured over a 5-cluster solution. The United States generally corresponds to lower cluster numbers in sample datasets. Wood Thrushes in different clusters did not show significantly different responses to tree cover, forest height, or elevation, but Wood Thrushes in higher cluster numbers (southeastern Ontario) showed a more negative response to roadsides than in other clusters. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 16. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are shown for 7-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets. Southeastern Ontario generally corresponds to higher cluster numbers in sample datasets. Note that for some sample datasets, a smaller number of clusters was favoured over a 7-cluster solution. The United States generally corresponds to lower cluster numbers in sample datasets. Geographically weighted regression model coefficients for all modeled land cover types are negative because the models did not include a y intercept, but the deciduous land cover type (i.e. Wood Thrush habitat) is least negative on average among land cover classes. Responses to land cover type were more negative for larger cluster numbers (southeastern Ontario) than lower cluster numbers (United States), probably because on average Wood Thrush numbers were greater in the United States. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Figure 17. Mean \pm standard deviation of effect size of different variables used in cluster analyses, separated by cluster, showing how a species responds to the same environmental variable(s) differently in different clusters (parts of the species' range). Results are shown for 7-cluster analysis of individual sample datasets, after removing land cover categorical predictors. Southeastern Ontario generally corresponds to higher cluster numbers in sample datasets. Note that for some sample datasets, a smaller number of clusters was favoured over a 7-cluster solution. The United States generally corresponds to lower cluster numbers in sample datasets. Wood Thrushes in different clusters did not show significantly different responses to tree cover, forest height, or elevation, but Wood Thrushes in higher cluster numbers (southeastern Ontario) showed a more negative response to roadsides than in other clusters. However, across different sample data sets, the overlap (or lack thereof) in predicted responses does not remain consistent, suggesting that Wood Thrush does not respond consistently differently to the 10 predictors in different parts of its range.

Regional Models of Wood Thrush Abundance for Landis Scenarios

The full BRT model, 2000-m-scale BRT model, and selected-scales BRT model had similar accuracy in predicting Wood Thrush abundance at points not used in training the BRTs. Overall, the selected-scales BRT was judged to be the best BRT in the combination of higher cross-validation correlation, calibration intercept closer to 0, and slope closer to 1. The exceedance BRT had a lower model deviance than other BRTs but did not perform as well in cross-validation correlation or its calibration intercept and slope values; thus, including effects of exceedance at the expense of a larger number of available point counts for modelling did not provide net benefits when predicting Wood Thrush abundance (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Residual deviance, cross validation correlation, and intercept and slope from the regression of predicted versus observed Wood Thrush abundance, for different boosted regression tree (BRT) models of Wood Thrush abundance in eastern Canada. Better predictive ability is associated with lower residual deviance, higher cross validation correlation, calibration intercept closer to 0, and calibration slope closer to 1. The full BRT model, 2000-m-scale BRT model, and selected-scales BRT model had similar predictive accuracy.

The most important predictors were proportions of (land within 150 - 2000 m consisting of) deciduous forest, swamp, shrubland, cultivated lands, and coniferous forest; whether a point count was within 150 m of any road and separately within 150 m of a major traffic road; mean point-level forest age and biomass within 2000 m; and elevation. Wood Thrush were on average most abundant when up to 80 % of land within 150 m consisted of swamps, when shrublands or coniferous forests comprised no more than 20 % of land within 2000 m, and with increasing deciduous forest cover within 150 m. Cultivated land and grassland were less important, but Wood Thrush increased with % cultivated lands within 1000 m, suggesting that they will use agricultural landscapes. Wood Thrush were less abundant at point counts within 150 m of roads in general, but the decrease was smaller within 150 m of major traffic roads: after accounting for roads, urban land within 2000 m had negligible influence on Wood Thrush. Wood Thrush were most abundant between 100 and 500 m above sea level. Wood Thrush declined when mean forest age within 2000 m was 20 – 60 years old, increased in forests < 20 years old, but generally increased with mean stand age and live aboveground biomass within 2000 m (Figure 19, Table 5).

Table 5. Relative influence of variables in the final boosted regression tree model chosen for predicting current and future Wood Thrush abundance and distribution in Landis scenarios in Quebec, New Brunswick, and Nova Scotia.

Predictor	Relative Influence (%)
Swamp 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of swamp)	19.62
Shrub 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of swamp)	13.97
Deciduous 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of deciduous forest > 20 years old)	10.41
Grassland 1000 m (proportion of land within 1 km consisting of grassland)	7.86
Cultivated 1000 m (land within 1 km consisting of all cultivated lands)	6.94
Stand Age 2000 m (mean forest stand age within 2 km)	5.99
Roadside 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from any road)	5.85
Major Road 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from high traffic roads)	5.77
Live Stand Biomass 2000 m (mean biomass within 2 km)	5.26
Elevation (m above sea level) (local value)	4.82
Coniferous 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of coniferous forest > 20 years old)	3.85
Mixed-wood 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of mixed-wood forest > 20 years old)	3.24
Wetland 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of all treed and non-treed wetland)	1.62
Water 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of open water)	1.28
Barren 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of barren land)	1.04
Urban 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of urban land)	0.93

Topographic Position Index (local value)	0.60
Slope (local value)	0.59
Terrain Ruggedness Index (local value)	0.34
Orchard 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of orchards)	0.02

Figure 19. Partial dependence plots showing the relationship between y (predicted $\log[\text{Wood Thrush density}]$) and each of the 10 most important variables from the selected-scale boosted regression tree model predicting this species' density in eastern Canada.

The direction of effect sizes and relative influence of different predictors were similar for the full and selected-scale BRT models, which had similar predictive accuracy to the 2000-m scale BRT. Local % deciduous forest within 150 m of point counts had more influence than deciduous forest at larger spatial scales in these BRT models, but Wood Thrush increased with deciduous forest within 150 m. Higher densities of Wood Thrush are predicted by BRTs in southwestern Ontario and southern Quebec than in New Brunswick or Nova Scotia (Figures 20 - 24).

Figure 20. Map of current Wood Thrush predicted densities (males/ha) within the kernel-density-estimated range (off-white to green) of the Wood Thrush in southern Ontario, within Bird Conservation Region 12.

Figure 21. Map of current Wood Thrush predicted densities (males/ha) within the kernel-density-estimated range (off-white to green) of the Wood Thrush in southern Ontario, within Bird Conservation Region 13.

Figure 22. Map of current Wood Thrush predicted densities (males/ha) within the kernel-density-estimated range (off-white to green) of the Wood Thrush in southern Quebec.

Figure 23. Map of current Wood Thrush predicted densities (males/ha) within the kernel-density-estimated range (off-white to green) of the Wood Thrush in southern New Brunswick.

Figure 24. Map of current Wood Thrush predicted densities (males/ha) within the kernel-density-estimated range (off-white to green) of the Wood Thrush in southern Nova Scotia.

Regional Models of Wood Thrush Abundance for the ALCES Online Scenario

When two variants of the selected-scales BRT model excluding stand biomass were run based on predictor values at 200-m or 250-m resolution (*ALCES 200*, *ALCES 250*), the *ALCES 200* BRT had slightly higher prediction accuracy (cross-validation correlation = 0.22) than the *ALCES 250* BRT (cross-validation correlation = 0.20) in predicting Wood Thrush abundance at points not used in training the BRTs. Predicted versus observed Wood Thrush abundance approached a 1:1 ratio (calibration intercept closer to 0, and slope closer to 1) more closely in the *ALCES 250* BRT model. As Wood Thrush abundance was predicted from the ALCES Online scenario using the *ALCES 200* BRT model, Wood Thrush populations appear to be underpredicted by the *ALCES 200* BRT model (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Residual deviance, cross validation correlation, and intercept and slope from the regression of predicted versus observed Wood Thrush abundance, for different boosted regression tree (BRT) models of Wood Thrush using predictors available in the ALCES Online land use simulator. Better predictive ability is associated with lower residual deviance, higher cross validation correlation, calibration intercept closer to 0, and calibration slope closer to 1. The BRT models were based on predictor values extracted to points from 200-m and 250-m resolution rasters.

The most important predictors of Wood Thrush in eastern Canada in the *ALCES 200* BRT model were proportions of (land within 150 - 2000 m consisting of) deciduous forest, swamp, and shrubland, and whether a point count was within 150 m of any road and separately within 150 m of a major traffic road. Wood Thrush were on average most abundant when deciduous forests comprised about 60 % of land within 150 m of point counts, up to 70 % of land within 150 m consisted of swamps, and when shrublands comprised no more than 20 % of land within 2000 m. Wood Thrush were more abundant within 150 m of major traffic roads, but after accounting for this influence were less abundant at point counts within 150 m of roads in general. Wood Thrush increased with elevation to 200 m above sea level, then declined with further increases in elevation. Wood Thrush were most abundant in forests that were at least 50 years old and increased with mean stand age within 2000 m but were slightly more abundant in

shrublands (mean stand age 2000 m < 20 years old) than in forests 20 – 60 years old (mean stand age 2000 m = 20 – 60 years old) (Figure 26, Table 6).

Table 6. Relative influence of variables in the final boosted regression tree model chosen for predicting current and future Wood Thrush abundance and distribution in the ALCES Online scenario run in Ontario.

Predictor Extracted from Rasters at 200-m Resolution	Relative Influence (%)
Swamp 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of swamp)	21.70
Shrub 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of shrubland)	17.99
Deciduous 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of deciduous forest > 20 years old)	10.12
Major Road 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from high traffic roads)	9.86
Roadside 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from any road)	7.92
Cultivated 1000 m (proportion of land within 1 km consisting of all cultivated lands)	6.93
Elevation (m above sea level) (local value)	5.08
Stand Age 2000 m (mean forest stand age within 2 km)	4.95
Grassland 1000 m (proportion of land within 1 km consisting of grassland)	3.82
Coniferous 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of coniferous forest > 20 years old)	2.78
Mixed-wood 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of mixed-wood forest > 20 years old)	2.69
Barren 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of barren land)	1.52
Wetland 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of all treed and non-treed wetland)	1.49
Water 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of open water)	1.20
Urban 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of urban land)	0.78
Slope (local value)	0.45
Topographic Position Index (local value)	0.38
Terrain Ruggedness Index (local value)	0.32
Orchard 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of orchards)	0.00

Figure 26. Partial dependence plots showing the relationship between y (predicted $\log[\text{Wood Thrush density}]$) and each of the 9 most important variables from the ALCES 200 boosted regression tree model predicting this species' density in eastern Canada. The ALCES 200 boosted regression tree model was also used to predict Wood Thrush abundance from the land use scenario run in ALCES Online. Swamp.150m = mean proportion of land within 150 m of point counts classified as swamp. Shrub.2000m = mean proportion of land within 2000 m of point counts classified as shrubland. Decid.2000m = mean proportion of land within 2000 m of point counts classified as deciduous forest. Grassland.1000m = mean proportion of land within 1000 m of point counts classified as grassland. Structure_Stand_Age.2000m = mean forest stand age within 2000 m of point counts. Roadside150 = Whether a point count is within 150 m of any roadside (=1) or not (=0). Cult.1000m = mean proportion of land within 1000 m of point counts classified as agricultural land. MajorRoad150 = Whether a point count is within 150 m of a primary road (e.g. highway) (=1) or not (=0). Elev = elevation (m) at each point count location. Relative influence of each variable in parentheses.

The direction of effect sizes and relative influence of different predictors differed substantially between the *ALCES 200* and *ALCES 250* BRT models. Although the three most influential predictors (swamp, shrubland, deciduous forest) remained the same, the direction of effects of swamp and shrubland amounts changed. Wood Thrush were on average most abundant when deciduous forests comprised about 60 - 100 % of land within 2000 m of point counts, or when 20 - 100 % of land within 150 m consisted of swamps, or when shrublands comprised 20 - 100 % of land within 2000 m. The response of Wood Thrush abundance to major roads and any roadside within 150 m was similar between the two BRTs. Wood Thrush decreased with increasing mean stand age within 2000 m, but stand age had negligible influence in the *ALCES 250* BRT. Despite this, due to the positive response of Wood Thrush to shrubland amount, the *ALCES 250* BRT would be more likely to predict a positive response of Wood Thrush to decreasing stand age from disturbances than the *ALCES 200* BRT, had it been possible to run the *ALCES* Online scenario at 250-m resolution (Figures 26 – 27, Tables 6 - 7).

Table 7. Relative influence of variables at 250-m resolution in a boosted regression tree model otherwise identical to the model used for predicting Wood Thrush abundance in the ALCES Online scenario run in Ontario.

Predictor Extracted from Rasters at 250-m Resolution	Relative Influence (%)
Swamp 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of swamp)	23.68
Shrub 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of shrubland)	19.73
Deciduous 150 m (proportion of land within 150 m consisting of deciduous forest > 20 years old)	13.08
Grassland 1000 m (land within 1 km consisting of grassland)	8.11
Cultivated 1000 m (land within 1 km consisting of all cultivated lands)	8.13
Roadside 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from any road)	7.38
Major Road 150 (point count or pixel \leq 150 m from high traffic roads)	9.53
Elevation (m above sea level) (local value)	3.40
Coniferous 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of coniferous forest > 20 years old)	2.52
Mixed-wood 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of mixed-wood forest > 20 years old)	2.15
Stand Age 2000 m (mean forest stand age within 2 km)	1.81
Wetland 2000 m (land within 2 km consisting of any wetland)	0.44
Water 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of open water)	0.03
Barren 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of barren land)	0.00
Orchard 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of orchards)	0.00
Urban 2000 m (proportion of land within 2 km consisting of urban land)	0.00
Slope (local value)	0.00
Topographic Position Index (local value)	0.00

Figure 27. Partial dependence plots showing the relationship between y (predicted $\log[\text{Wood Thrush density}]$) and each of the 9 most important variables from the ALCES 250 boosted regression tree model predicting this species' density in eastern Canada. The ALCES 250 boosted regression tree model was not used to predict Wood Thrush abundance from the land use scenario run in ALCES Online, but was run to determine how predictions based on the ALCES Online scenario might be affected by the switch from model predictors at 250 m to 200 m resolution. Swamp.150m = mean proportion of land within 150 m of point counts classified as swamp. Shrub.2000m = mean proportion of land within 2000 m of point counts classified as shrubland. Decid.2000m = mean proportion of land within 2000 m of point counts classified as deciduous forest. Grassland.1000m = mean proportion of land within 1000 m of point counts classified as grassland. Structure_Stand_Age.2000m = mean forest stand age within 2000 m of point counts. Roadside150 = Whether a point count is within 150 m of any roadside (=1) or not (=0). Cult.1000m = mean proportion of land within 1000 m of point counts classified as agricultural land. MajorRoad150 = Whether a point count is within 150 m of a primary road (e.g. highway) (=1) or not (=0). Elev = elevation (m) at each point count location. Relative influence of each variable in parentheses.

Future Wood Thrush Abundance and Distribution in Landis Scenarios

The Wood Thrush was projected to at least double from 2020 – 2100 within the study area in southern Quebec, under all Landis scenarios that were run. In the study area, Wood Thrush increased from 612,380 to 1,273,375 - 1,394,910 males. Harvest reduced potential habitat for Wood Thrush, and habitat increased with moderate amounts of climate change (RCP45 scenarios) (Table 8).

Table 8. Projected Wood Thrush population size in southern Quebec in 2100 A. D., based on five simulation runs of six harvest and climate change scenarios in Landis.

Scenario	Mean population size in 2100 from 5 simulation runs
RCP 8.5 no harvest	1,959,455 Best-case scenario
RCP 4.5 no harvest	1,956,772
Baseline climate no harvest	1,900,803
RCP 8.5 with harvest	1,899,649 Medium-case scenario
RCP 4.5 with harvest	1,875,860
Baseline climate with harvest	1,815,598 Worst-case scenario

The Wood Thrush was projected to increase from 2020 – 2100 within the study area in southern New Brunswick, under all Landis scenarios that were run. In the study area, Wood

Thrush increased from 169,926 to 261,693 - 461,209 males. Potential habitat for Wood Thrush increased in warmer climate change scenarios (Table 9).

Table 9. Projected Wood Thrush population size in southern New Brunswick in 2100 A. D. based on five simulation runs of three harvest and climate change scenarios in Landis.

Scenario	Mean population size in 2100 from 5 simulation runs	
RCP 8.5 with harvest	458,950	Best-case scenario
RCP 4.5 with harvest	325,133	Medium-case scenario
Baseline climate with harvest	260,676	Worst-case scenario

The Wood Thrush was projected to increase from 2020 – 2100 within the study area in southern Nova Scotia, under all Landis scenarios that were run. In the study area, Wood Thrush increased from 71,533 to 199,405 – 268,721 males. Potential habitat for Wood Thrush increased in warmer climate change scenarios and with increased harvest (Table 10).

Table 10. Projected Wood Thrush population size in southern Nova Scotia in 2100 A. D., based on five simulation runs of three harvest and climate change scenarios in Landis.

Scenario	Mean population size in 2100 from 5 simulation runs	
RCP 85 Historic Clear-cutting Rates	268,721	Best-case scenario
RCP 85 Ecosystem-based Forest Management	244,551	
RCP 45 Historic Clear-cutting Rates	231,126	
RCP 45 Ecosystem-based Forest Management	219,570	
Baseline climate Historic Clear-cutting Rates	205,326	Medium-case scenario
Baseline climate No Harvest	204,783	
RCP 85 No Harvest	204,357	
Baseline climate Ecosystem-based Forest Management	201,058	
RCP 45 No Harvest	199,405	Worst-case scenario

Future Wood Thrush Abundance and Distribution in the ALCES Online Scenario

In the ALCES Online scenario that was run, land cover types were not permanently converted to other land cover types by disturbance. Forest age was set back, so forests were temporarily converted to shrubland by harvest and in a few forest management units, fire;

however, forests were allowed to grow back after all disturbances in the scenario. Forest age was also set back by spruce budworm outbreaks; however, mean forest age increased from 2020 – 2070 in all simulation runs (Figures 28 - 29).

Figure 28. Projected increase in mean forest age per 200-m pixel within the Wood Thrush's Ontario range from 2020 – 2070, based on 5 simulation runs of a single land use scenario in ALCES Online. The land use scenario simulated harvest and spruce budworm disturbances, and in three forest management units fire, based on the 10 most recent available years of data for provincial forest management units and private woodlots outside of forest management units within the Wood Thrush's Ontario range.

Figure 29. Projected change in mean proportion of land within 2000 m of each 200-m pixel consisting of shrublands (wooded lands < 20 years old) within the Wood Thrush's Ontario range from 2020 – 2070, based on 5 simulation runs of a single land use scenario in ALCES Online. The land use scenario simulated harvest and spruce budworm disturbances, and in three forest management units fire, based on the 10 most recent available years of data for provincial forest management units and private woodlots outside of forest management units within the Wood Thrush's Ontario range. Clear-cutting and fires set back forest age to 10 years old, creating new shrublands, while other disturbances (selective logging, shelterwood harvest, budworm outbreaks) set back forest age to 20 – 60 years old without creating new, temporary shrublands.

The Wood Thrush was projected to increase from 2020 – 2070 within its Ontario range, based on the ALCES Online scenario that was run. In Bird Conservation Region 12, Wood Thrush increased by 30 % from 254,841 to 330,945 (based on 5 simulation runs). In Bird Conservation Region 13, Wood Thrush increased by 16 % from 255,597 to 296,377 (based on 5 simulation runs) (Figures 30 – 31).

Figure 30. Projected Wood Thrush increase in Bird Conservation Region 12 within its Ontario range from 2020 – 2070, based on 5 simulation runs of a single land use scenario in ALCES Online. The land use scenario simulated harvest and spruce budworm disturbances based on the 10 most recent available years of data for provincial forest management units in Bird Conservation Region 12.

Figure 31. Projected Wood Thrush increase in Bird Conservation Region 13 within its Ontario range from 2020 – 2070, based on 5 simulation runs of a single land use scenario in ALCES Online. The land use scenario simulated harvest and spruce budworm disturbances based on the 10 most recent available years of data for provincial forest management units and private woodlots outside of forest management units in Bird Conservation Region 13.

Conservation Planning for Wood Thrush Based on Landis Scenarios

Output from each Zonation exercise included a raster of the study area where locations have been assigned ranks from 0 - 1 according to the locations' priority for conservation or management as habitat for Wood Thrush. Locations were generally assigned higher ranks if locations supported higher predicted Wood Thrush densities in a current and/or future density layer or if there was greater confidence (lower standard deviation) in the density estimates at a location. Other output from each Zonation exercise included data for generating a runtime plot showing what proportion of the total summed values of a given feature (current or future density layer) remained as an increasing proportion of cells in the study area was “removed” from consideration. Cells with higher ranks remained in study areas the longest (e.g. rank > 0.9 = remaining 10 % of cells when 90 % of cells are removed from a study area) and the rank of a cell indicates the proportion of cells in the study area with lower ranks that will be removed before that cell. Thus, it was possible to know what proportion of the current or future population remained as more land was “removed” and determine the amount and location of lands necessary to protect a certain proportion of the current or future population. Although the total current or future population starts to decrease when the first cells are removed during a Zonation exercise, predicted density in some parts of the study area was low enough that some lands were “removed” before the current or future population started dropping significantly below 100%.

In the Landis and Zonation study areas in southern Quebec, southern New Brunswick, and southern Nova Scotia, pixels receiving higher ranks and prioritization were similar across the four Zonation exercises in each study area. However, the amount of land required to maintain the current Wood Thrush population was very different across the four exercises (Figures 32 – 40).

In southern Quebec, when only the current population was considered, 15, 39, 66, and >99 % of the study area (12,258,363 ha) would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (612,380 males). The best-case, medium-case, and worst-case Landis scenarios predicted a larger Wood Thrush population in 2100 A.D. than the current population (respectively 106, 95, and 91 % more males). The corresponding Zonation scenarios that also considered future population estimated that less land needs to be prioritized for protection or management in the corresponding Zonation exercises (best case: 10, 23, 43, and 88 %; medium case: 9, 23, 43, and 88 %; worst case: 9, 23, 43, and 88 %) to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (Figures 33 - 34).

Figure 32. Maps of southern Quebec in which individual locations (250-m cells) are coloured according to their priority for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat under present and future environmental conditions. Darker colours indicate locations with higher priority (on a scale from 0 to 1) as habitat for Wood Thrush. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Quebec. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Quebec, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 33. Multi-colour maps indicating what areas to prioritize as habitat for different percentages of the current Wood Thrush population in southern Quebec: dark red = areas necessary to maintain 50 % of current population as of 2019 (highest-priority areas) in the study area under a given Zonation exercise; dark orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 75 % of the current population; light orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 90 % of the current population; light yellow = areas needed to maintain an additional 75 – 100 % of the current population (lowest priority areas); light blue = areas that are not required for protection of 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population in southern Quebec, assuming that the most suitable habitats are protected. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Quebec. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Quebec, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 34. Runtime plots showing the proportion of the current and future Wood Thrush population remaining in its current range in southern Quebec as lands (250-m cells) are removed from consideration for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat, under four Zonation exercises. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Quebec, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels, when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat. Since population projections were similar across different Landis scenarios, the amount of land that can be removed barely differed in Zonation exercises based on the best, medium, and worst-case scenarios.

In southern New Brunswick, when only the current population was considered, 18, 42, 68, and >99 % of the study area (6,431,194 ha) would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (169,926 males). The best-case, medium-case, and worst-case Landis scenarios predicted a larger Wood Thrush population in 2100 A.D. than

the current population (respectively 126, 64, and 30 % more males). The corresponding Zonation scenarios that also considered future population estimated that less land needs to be prioritized for protection or management in the corresponding Zonation exercises (best case: 7, 18, 31, and 80 %; medium case: 7, 18, 31, and 79 %; worst case: 7, 18, 31, and 79 %) to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (Figures 36 - 37).

Figure 35. Maps of southern New Brunswick in the current estimated range of the Wood Thrush, which individual locations (250-m cells) are coloured according to their priority for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat under present and future environmental conditions. Darker colours indicate locations with higher priority (on a scale from 0 to 1) as habitat for Wood Thrush. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in New Brunswick. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern New Brunswick, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 36. Multi-colour maps indicating what areas to prioritize as habitat for different percentages of the current Wood Thrush population in its current estimated range in southern New Brunswick: dark red = areas necessary to maintain 50 % of current population as of 2019 (highest-priority areas) in the study area under a given Zonation exercise; dark orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 75 % of the current population; light orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 90 % of the current population; light yellow = areas needed to maintain an additional 75 – 100 % of the current population (lowest priority areas); light blue = areas that are not required for protection of 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population in southern New Brunswick, assuming that the most suitable habitats are protected. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in New Brunswick. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern New Brunswick, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 37. Runtime plots showing the proportion of the current and future Wood Thrush population remaining in its current range in southern New Brunswick as lands (250-m cells) are removed from consideration for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat, under four Zonation exercises. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern New Brunswick, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels, when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

In southern Nova Scotia, when only the current population was considered, 18, 43, 67, and >99 % of the study area (5,085,488 ha) would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (71,533 males). The best-case, medium-case, and worst-case Landis scenarios predicted a larger Wood Thrush population in 2100 A.D. than the current population (respectively 275, 187, and 179 % more males). The corresponding Zonation scenarios that also considered future population estimated that less land needs to be prioritized for protection or management in the corresponding Zonation exercises (best case: 3, 8, 16, and 50 %; medium case: 3, 8, 15, and 50 %; worst case: 2, 8, 15, and 49 %) to maintain 50, 75, 90,

and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (Figures 39 - 40).

Figure 38. Maps of southern Nova Scotia in the current estimated range of the Wood Thrush, which individual locations (250-m cells) are coloured according to their priority for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat under present and future environmental conditions. Darker colours indicate locations with higher priority (on a scale from 0 to 1) as habitat for Wood Thrush. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Nova Scotia. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Nova Scotia, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 39. Multi-colour maps indicating what areas to prioritize as habitat for different percentages of the current Wood Thrush population in its current estimated range in southern Nova Scotia: dark red = areas necessary to maintain 50 % of current population as of 2019 (highest-priority areas) in the study area under a given Zonation exercise; dark orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 75 % of the current population; light orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 90 % of the current population; light yellow = areas needed to maintain an additional 75 – 100 % of the current population (lowest priority areas); light blue = areas that are not required for protection of 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population in southern Nova Scotia, assuming that the most suitable habitats are protected. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Nova Scotia. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Nova Scotia, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 40. Runtime plots showing the proportion of the current and future Wood Thrush population remaining in its current range in southern Nova Scotia as lands (250-m cells) are removed from consideration for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat, under four Zonation exercises. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Best = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the best-case Landis scenario; Medium = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the medium-case Landis scenario; Worst = based on current density + 2100 A. D. population from the worst-case Landis scenario. As the 2100 population was projected to be higher than the current population in southern Nova Scotia, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels, when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Conservation Planning for Wood Thrush Based on the ALCES Online Scenario

Within Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12 combined, when only the current population was considered, 25, 49, 71, and >99 % of the study area (17,087,944 ha) would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (254,841 males). The Wood Thrush population was predicted to be 30 % higher in 2070 A.D. than the current population, and the Zonation exercise that also considered future population estimated that 7, 15,

25, and 58 % of the study area would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (Figures 41 - 43).

Figure 41. Maps of Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12 within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario, in which individual locations (200-m cells) are coloured according to their priority for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat under present and future environmental conditions. Darker colours indicate locations with higher priority (on a scale from 0 to 1) as habitat for Wood Thrush. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Current plus 2070 = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Ontario. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 42. Multi-colour maps indicating what areas to prioritize as habitat for different percentages of the current Wood Thrush population in Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12: dark red = areas necessary to maintain 50 % of current population as of 2019 (highest-priority areas) in the study area under a given Zonation exercise; dark orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 75 % of the current population; light orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 90 % of the current population; light yellow = areas needed to maintain an additional 75 – 100 % of the current population (lowest priority areas); light blue = areas that are not required for protection of 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population in Bird Conservation Region 12, assuming that the most suitable habitats are protected. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Current plus 2070 = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Ontario. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 43. Runtime plots showing the proportion of the current and future Wood Thrush population remaining in Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12 as lands (200-m cells) are removed from consideration for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat, under two Zonation exercises. Zonation exercises: Left panel = based on current population density alone; right panel = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation Regions 8 and 12, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels, when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Within Bird Conservation Region 13, when only the current population was considered, 18, 42, 68, and >99 % of the study area (12,638,406 ha) would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (255,597 males). The Wood Thrush population was predicted to be 16 % higher in 2070 A.D. than the current population, and the Zonation exercise that also considered future population estimated that 10, 24, 41, and 83 % of the study area would be required to maintain 50, 75, 90, and 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population (Figures 44 - 46).

Figure 44. Maps of Bird Conservation Region 13 in which individual locations (200-m cells) are coloured according to their priority for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat under present and future environmental conditions. Darker colours indicate locations with higher priority (on a scale from 0 to 1) as habitat for Wood Thrush. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Current plus 2070 = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Ontario. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation 13, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 45. Multi-colour maps indicating what areas to prioritize as habitat for different percentages of the current Wood Thrush population in Bird Conservation Region 13: dark red = areas necessary to maintain 50 % of current population as of 2019 (highest-priority areas) in the study area under a given Zonation exercise; dark orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 75 % of the current population; light orange = additional areas necessary to maintain up to 90 % of the current population; light yellow = areas needed to maintain an additional 75 – 100 % of the current population (lowest priority areas); light blue = areas that are not required for protection of 100 % of the current Wood Thrush population in Bird Conservation Region 13, assuming that the most suitable habitats are protected. Zonation exercises: Current = based on current population density alone; Current plus 2070 = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. Gray lines = provincial/state boundaries for different Bird Conservation Regions in North America. Black lines = existing protected areas in Ontario. Note that high-priority habitat for Wood Thrush generally is located outside of existing protected areas. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation 12, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Figure 46. Runtime plots showing the proportion of the current and future Wood Thrush population remaining in Bird Conservation Region 13 as lands (200-m cells) are removed from consideration for conservation or management as Wood Thrush habitat, under two Zonation exercises. Zonation exercises: Left panel = based on current population density alone; right panel = based on current density + 2070 A. D. population from baseline ALCES Online scenario. As the 2070 population was projected to be higher than the current population in Bird Conservation 13, less land was required to maintain various percentages of the current population levels, when future distribution of the Wood Thrush was also used to prioritize lands as habitat.

Discussion

Management Units Identified from Geographically Weighted (GW) Models and Cluster Analysis

There was insufficient biological evidence from geographically weighted models to justify more than a single management unit for developing regional models of Wood Thrush abundance in Canada. This result was not surprising since the Wood Thrush currently has a limited distribution in Canada and there was no evidence in the literature suggesting that Wood Thrush used habitat differently in different parts of its Canadian range.

Regional Models of Wood Thrush Abundance: Caveats

While predictor effects from the BRTs used as regional Wood Thrush models can be difficult to interpret, partial dependence plots from the BRTs suggested that the most important predictors' effects were consistent with effects identified in past Wood Thrush studies. Positive effects of deciduous forest amount within 125 - 150 m were consistent with many studies in which Wood Thrush were more abundant in larger forest fragments (Rich et al., 1994; Sargent et al., 2003; Richmond et al., 2012). Positive effects of small amounts of shrubland within 2000 m were consistent with use of shrublands and disturbed forests by fledgling and juvenile Wood Thrushes (Anders et al., 1998; Rivera et al., 1998; Powell et al., 2000; Lang et al., 2002; Schlossberg et al., 2018). Positive effects of swampland amount within 125 – 150 m were consistent with past studies suggesting that Wood Thrush prefer moist forest conditions (Bertin, 1977), but that areas dominated entirely by swamp may be less suitable, possibly if removal of leaf litter and understory vegetation by floods at lower elevations reduced prey availability and potential nest sites for Wood Thrush (Sargent et al., 2003). Negative effects of roads in general were consistent with studies in which Wood Thrush were less abundant at forest edges bordering paved roads and in landscapes with more forest fragmentation (Rich et al., 1994).

Previous studies have suggested that acid rain impacts on eastern deciduous forests could have impacts on Wood Thrush food supplies (Graveland, 1990; Reynolds and Perrins, 2010), egg production, nesting success and nestling survival (Graveland and Drent, 1997; Pabian and Brittingham, 2011), making it useful to include measures of acid rain on habitat quality for

Wood Thrush. The Wood Thrush model using exceedance values among its predictors had a lower model deviance than other BRTs but did not perform as well in cross-validation correlation or its calibration intercept and slope values; thus, including effects of exceedance at the expense of a larger number of available point counts for modelling did not provide net benefits when predicting Wood Thrush abundance. The exceedance layers that were used to measure acid rain impacts were preliminary data products, so a more complete data product in the future with greater coverage could be used to rerun models with acid rain impacts. Alternatively, as acid deposition tends to be higher at higher elevations and in landscapes with forest fragmentation (Hames et al., 2002) – where Wood Thrush were generally less abundant in the current and previous studies – the effects of acid rain may have been minimized on Wood Thrush.

Some caveats exist with respect to the ability of the models to predict Wood Thrush abundance within its breeding habitats. Beyond the effects of acid rain which were considered, there could be additional effects of habitat fragmentation not accounted for by land cover types at different spatial scales or by distance from the nearest road, such as edge effects associated with different types of edge or measurements of connectivity (Rich et al., 1994; Sargent et al., 2003). Response of Wood Thrush to specific types of deciduous forest was not modelled, mainly because there were concerns that tree species layers available at 250-m resolution (Beaudoin et al., 2014) would not be accurately represented in smaller woodlots in the recent land cover data at 30-m resolution that was used in the models (AAFC, 2021). The response of Wood Thrush to different types of temporary forest disturbances (fire, insects, different harvest regimes) (Rivera et al., 1998; Powell et al., 2000; Simons et al., 2000; Lang et al., 2002) was not modelled since consistent, fine-scale data across the range of the Wood Thrush was not available for all provinces.

The main caveat of the regional models used to predict current and future Wood Thrush abundance is the assumption that higher densities of Wood Thrush occur in habitats with more resources and higher survival and reproductive success (Rosenfeld and Hatfield, 2006). While there is a theoretical basis for species to settle in higher densities in habitats with more resources and better prospects for individual fitness (i.e. “ideal free distribution”: Fretwell and Lucas, 1970), species may also actively settle in suboptimal unsuitable habitats that serve as ecological traps because they resemble better habitats in some habitat cues (Battin, 2004). Ecological traps may be more likely to occur in rapidly changing man-made landscapes (Battin, 2004). Alternatively, dominant individuals may successfully occupy the best habitats at lower densities, forcing subordinate individuals to crowd into less suitable habitats, which are then mistakenly identified as suitable by human researchers (Fretwell and Lucas, 1970). Finally, habitat selection and/or individual fitness may be positively correlated with the “best” habitats up under a threshold density of individuals, beyond which habitat selection and quality become density-dependent (Hostetler et al., 2015).

For SAR with recovery plans in which 1) important habitats for recovery have been identified and 2) CH has been designated, CH is still rarely based on actual measures of survivorship, productivity, or population viability (e. g. 1 % of species in Australia, Canada, and

the United States for which CH had been defined [Camaclang et al., 2015]; 15 % of 53 Canadian vertebrate species with recovery plans including CH [Lemieux Lefebvre et al., 2018]). The reason that CH is usually not based on survivorship, productivity, or population viability is that data for any of these metrics is frequently unavailable for most species and is usually limited in extent relative to the population of interest (Robinson et al., 2014). However, if habitat quality and habitat densities of a species are not positively correlated, then abundance data alone will not be sufficient to identify the most important habitats and may indeed result in selection of unsuitable areas for protection (with or without CH designation) that do not help SAR recover (Battin, 2004). With respect to Wood Thrush, some but not all areas in Bird Conservation Region 13 in Ontario having higher current or future predicted densities do occur in areas dominated by agricultural or urban lands. Such areas might support relatively high Wood Thrush densities since Wood Thrush will nest in fragments as small as 1 ha (Evans et al., 2020), but these areas are likely to be population sinks or ecological traps if past studies of nesting success in fragmented forest landscapes hold true (Roth and Johnson, 1993; Trine, 1998; Lloyd et al., 2005; Phillips et al., 2005).

Concerns about predictions from abundance models being decoupled from true habitat quality may be resolved by changing the way that predictors are selected for abundance modelling. In the current study, the final model selected for predicting current and future Wood Thrush densities in Landis and ALCES Online was the “selected scales” model in which amounts of land cover and forest structure predictors were only modelled at a single spatial scale where each predictor had the strongest influence on Wood Thrush abundance. In the “selected scales” model, the effect of deciduous forest cover was modelled at the local scale within the 250 m x 250 m or 200 x 200 m cell containing each point count, and for either pixel size, Wood Thrush increased with the proportion of the pixel dominated by deciduous forest. The spatial scale at which deciduous forest cover was modelled may explain why there were still some areas in agricultural or urban landscapes with high predicted Wood Thrush densities: forest fragments that were large enough for a 250 m x 250 m or 200 x 200 m cell to be dominated by deciduous forests could support higher Wood Thrush densities. Future regional models could instead model predictors at the spatial scale where those predictors have the strongest influence on Wood Thrush reproductive success and/or individual survival. Wood Thrush nest success and survival in past studies was associated with larger amounts of deciduous forest and less fragmentation at larger spatial scales (Burke and Nol, 2000; Austen et al., 2001; Lee et al., 2002; Driscoll et al., 2005; Richmond et al., 2012; Bonnot et al., 2013). Beyond modelling land cover predictors explicitly at the spatial scales associated with higher reproductive success and/or individual survival in past studies, regional models could assess the effects of variables other than land cover amount (e.g. distance to forest edge [Friesen et al., 1999; Kaiser and Lindell, 2007; Newell and Kostalos, 2007]; type of forest edge [Schlossberg et al., 2018]; climate variables associated with drought [Vernasco et al., 2018]) that are both associated with forest fragmentation and with reproductive success and/or survival of individuals.

Further, while BRTs were used to model Wood Thrush abundance in the current study, based on the data available for modelling, there is no reason why another type of model couldn't be used to predict Wood Thrush abundance or occupancy, or why additional types of models

couldn't be used to predict actual habitat quality as measured by reproductive success, individual survival, or population viability (Camaclang et al., 2015; Lemieux Lefebvre et al., 2018). If there is sufficient data for modelling reproductive success and/or survival, models that predict these metrics could be used to complement the abundance models. Either models of Wood Thrush reproductive success and/or survival could be integrated with the abundance models in a single analysis (e. g. integrated population modelling [Schaub and Abadi, 2011]), or models of reproductive success and/or survival could be used to generate a separate set of maps showing predicted fitness of individual Wood Thrush. These fitness maps could be compared to predicted density maps to evaluate how well predicted Wood Thrush densities and fitness are correlated. If the variables used to estimate fitness can be derived from variables used in land use simulators, it may be possible to predict changes in Wood Thrush fitness due to landscape and climate changes over time. Fitness maps could be used alongside density maps as feature layers within Zonation when prioritizing and identifying the most important habitats for Wood Thrush.

A final caveat of the regional Wood Thrush models concerns estimation of current and future populations based on the suitability of breeding habitats. The population that is being estimated is the potential rather than the actual population, since some of the suitable habitats may be currently unoccupied (Thomas and Kunin, 1999; Camaclang et al., 2015). This situation is especially likely for migratory birds like the Wood Thrush that spend most of the year outside of Canada, where their populations can be reduced by sources of mortality during migration and overwintering.

Wood Thrush Abundance and Distribution in Future Land Use Scenarios: Caveats

The Wood Thrush was generally projected to increase in future land use scenarios run in either Landis or ALCES Online across its range in Canada. In all Landis study areas, larger Wood Thrush populations were associated with warming climate. Increased harvest rates were associated with lower future Wood Thrush populations in Quebec, which is consistent with studies in which Wood Thrush increased with forest age (Bertin, 1977; Evans et al., 2020) or declined with harvest (Simons et al., 2000; Kendrick et al., 2015). However, increased harvest rates were associated with higher future Wood Thrush populations in Nova Scotia. As there was only one scenario run in ALCES Online, there was no indication of how Wood Thrush would respond to harvest or a warming climate in Ontario. As only harvest scenarios with identical harvest practices were run in New Brunswick, there was no indication of how Wood Thrush would respond to different harvest rates in that province. The response of Wood Thrush populations outside of Ontario to a warming climate is consistent with projected responses of its deciduous forest habitats and growth rates to climate change at the expense of coniferous forests, especially under higher harvest rates (Taylor et al., 2018; Boulanger and Puigdevall, 2021). The positive trends in Wood Thrush obtained from two independent land use simulators are also encouraging with respect to recovery of this species; nevertheless, caveats to the use of land use simulation projections should be noted. The overarching point about using climate change and land use scenarios to project future populations of Wood Thrush or other SAR is that predictions are only as good as the assumptions underlying the scenarios being considered.

First, while Wood Thrush may benefit from a warming climate, climate change scenarios like the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios used by Landis only simulate “what if” CO₂ emissions increase to certain levels by 2100, causing the temperature increases that affect natural disturbance regime and stand dynamics (Moss et al., 2010). Depending on the activity, climate change adaptation might result in increases in Wood Thrush habitat (planting more deciduous tree species used by Wood Thrush) or decreases (actively planting or maintaining more coniferous tree species through fire suppression and pest control).

Second, Wood Thrush populations were projected to increase based on the levels of harvest that were simulated. Based on the habitat preferences of Wood Thrush for mature, less fragmented deciduous forests in this study and previous studies, the harvest levels simulated in Landis and ALCES Online were not sufficient to prevent average forest age from increasing, which allowed habitat for Wood Thrush to increase over time in harvested scenarios. A related and major caveat in Landis is that stand age is based on the oldest tree cohorts within a stand, so when harvest is less than 100 %, old cohorts within a stand can subsist and stand age continues to increase throughout the simulation. In ALCES Online, clear-cutting, shelterwood harvesting, and selective logging rates were based on GIS data from actual harvested forests from the last decade in different Forest Management Units and assumptions about harvest age were based on a small number of variables (mean harvest size, total decadal harvest, maximum % of harvest area disturbed for a small number of broad forest types). These harvest amounts can be less than the amounts that forestry companies are legally allowed to harvest within their Forest Management Plans submitted by companies. Due to socio-economic factors like economic downturns in commodity prices, planning forest growth to increase high-quality wood in the future, costs of road construction, labour shortages, land consultation for conducting harvests on First Nations lands, environmental campaigns to protect wildlife habitats, or wildlife habitat management by forestry companies (Gouvernement du Québec, 2020; Algonquin Forestry Authority, 2021; Bancroft Minden Forest Company, 2021), the forest areas harvested by forestry companies may end up being less than what the companies are legally permitted to harvest. Thus, simulated harvest rates based on GIS data (as in the ALCES Online scenario) may therefore underestimate realistic future harvest rates, which may result in lower Wood Thrush populations under more realistic scenarios. Landis can be used to simulate complex harvest regimes (e. g. Cadieux et al., 2020) but these harvest regimes are not realistic because they rarely consider socioeconomic factors. Rather than using land use simulation, forestry companies usually use harvest-scheduling software (e. g. Patchworks [<http://www.spatial.ca/products/index.html>]) that determines an optimal spatially explicit harvest plan considering tree growth rates and socioeconomic factors (e.g. socioeconomic) that must be considered in harvest plans (Sturtevant et al., 2007). Future land use scenarios in ALCES Online could use harvest plans developed in Patchworks to simulate more realistic scheduled harvest scenarios (Leston et al., 2020).

Third, simulations may have underestimated impacts of insect and fungal outbreaks on Wood Thrush habitats. Insect outbreaks are predicted to increase with global warming in Canada’s forests (Ghandi and Herms, 2010; Pureswaran et al., 2018), although there is considerable uncertainty in the extent of outbreaks of some species like spruce budworm in the Wood Thrush range (Boulanger et al., 2016a). Both Landis or ALCES Online scenarios

simulated the impacts of spruce budworm outbreaks on forest age and succession. While outbreaks set back forest age, spruce budworm does not target the deciduous forests used by Wood Thrush as breeding habitat, so this species may have had negligible effects on habitat for Wood Thrush. However, other insect species and insect-mediated fungal diseases like beech bark disease (Karschnik, 2014) that target deciduous trees may pose a greater threat to habitat for Wood Thrush. While eastern North American deciduous forests have been subject to natural outbreaks of spruce budworm and tent caterpillar (*Malacosoma disstria*), there are increasing numbers of exotic herbivorous insect species in those forests, with some like gypsy moth and emerald ash-leaf borer (*Agrilus planipennis*) producing large episodic outbreaks targeting deciduous tree species (Ghandi and Herms, 2010). Among the ecosystem effects these outbreaks could influence, a reduced average deciduous forest age could result in less habitat for Wood Thrush in the future. Alternatively, outbreaks of some defoliating insects within deciduous forests may be associated with increases in food for and increased reproductive success of deciduous forest songbirds (Holmes et al., 1986). The creation of small canopy gaps by insect outbreaks has created habitat for additional ground-nesting and insectivorous bird species in coniferous forests (Becker et al., 2008; Przepióra et al., 2020), which might allow Wood Thrush to expand into such forests in the future. Wood Thrush juveniles have used deciduous forests damaged by gypsy moth defoliation as habitat (Rivera et al., 1998), and Wood Thrush have increased in canopy gaps in hemlock forests infested by hemlock wooly adelgid (*Adelges tsugae*) (Becker et al., 2008).

Fourth, land use simulation may have overestimated the amount of future forest habitats available for Wood Thrush. The Landis and ALCES Online scenarios in this study only simulated temporary disturbances setting back forest age like harvest, budworm outbreaks, and fires. Simulated harvests were also limited to merchantable upland forests as opposed to swamps also used as Wood Thrush habitat. As a result, forests always could regenerate after simulated disturbance and average forest age increased over time. Without any forest losses to human footprint other than harvest, especially in swamps, the cumulative area of older forests increased over time, increasing potential habitat for Wood Thrush (Bertin, 1977; Evans et al., 2020). Conversion of forests to urban or agricultural lands would probably reduce habitat for Wood Thrush, although Wood Thrush can nest in fragments as small as 1 ha (Evans et al., 2020). Swamps used by Wood Thrush could also be vulnerable to conversion to urban or agricultural lands. The ALCES Online scenario run in this study simulated harvest as the only human footprint to make the scenario more comparable to the Landis scenarios. While habitat conversion was not simulated in the Wood Thrush study, future Landis scenarios could simulate permanent habitat conversion or at least habitat fragmentation due to simulated new roads (<https://github.com/Klemet>), and ALCES Online is versatile in modelling multiple disturbance types (Carlson et al., 2014; Carlson and Stelfox, 2014; Carlson et al., 2019).

Fifth, besides permanent habitat conversion to non-forest lands, the Landis and ALCES Online scenarios did not simulate effects of habitat fragmentation associated with urban or agricultural development, apart from the amounts of different land cover types within 150 – 2000 m. Wood Thrush abundance responded negatively to habitat fragmentation in past studies, with Wood Thrush more likely to occur and increase in larger forest fragments (Robbins et al., 1989),

further from forest edges near paved roads (Rich et al., 1994), in forests connected by corridors and not surrounded by fields (Sargent et al., 2003), and in landscapes with a greater proportion of forest (Richmond et al., 2012). Beyond decreases in Wood Thrush abundance with simulated fragmentation by urban and agricultural lands, there could be reductions in nest success due to nest predators or nest parasitism by Brown-headed Cowbirds in fragmented habitats (Trine, 1998; Powell and Knutson, 2006) and have increased with forest fragmentation by urban or agricultural land in some parts of the Wood Thrush range (Lloyd et al., 2005), albeit not everywhere (Friesen et al., 1999; Trine, 1998; Phillips et al., 2005). Wood Thrush survival might decline from predation by cats in urban and agricultural areas. Wood Thrush nesting success tends to increase with increased surrounding forest fragment size or forest cover (Burke and Nol, 2000; Driscoll et al., 2005; Richmond et al., 2012) and decrease with forest fragmentation and along forest edges (Weinberg and Roth, 1998; Hoover et al., 2005; Newell and Kostalos, 2007), although not in all areas (Friesen et al., 1999; Kaiser and Lindell, 2007). As a result of parasitism and predation, reduced nesting success, and lower survival, habitat that is predicted to support higher densities of Wood Thrush in the future may serve as population sinks for Wood Thrushes if that habitat is embedded within urban or agricultural lands. Beyond habitat conversion, nest predation, and parasitism associated with habitat fragmentation, over-browsing of understory vegetation by white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) populations could degrade or decrease Wood Thrush habitat (Rushing et al., 2020; COSEWIC, 2012). Although deer browsing was not considered in regional models or any land use scenarios in this study, effects of browsing on forest age and succession could be simulated in additional Landis scenarios (De Jager et al., 2017: <https://sites.google.com/site/Landismodel/extensions/browse-disturbance>).

Finally, the Landis and ALCES Online scenarios only considered potential changes to breeding habitat of Wood Thrush populations in Canada, and only based on the amount of broad forest types and distance from roads rather than including other fragmentation effects. Decreasing availability of stopover and winter habitats and increasing mortality within remnant non-breeding habitats are other mechanisms underlying declines in this species. Most Wood Thrushes overwinter in parts of Honduras and Costa Rica subject to heavy deforestation and weather events affecting plant productivity in winter forest habitats (Stanley et al., 2014; Rushing et al., 2016). Wood Thrush abundance on breeding grounds increased following increased vegetation productivity and winter forest habitat amount in the preceding winter (Rushing et al., 2016). If winter habitat is threatened by harvest or degraded by droughts, Wood Thrush could continue to decline despite increases in breeding habitat. If the area of suitable winter habitat used by a given Wood Thrush population were known and the amount and productivity of that habitat in the winter preceding a breeding survey year were included as predictors in Wood Thrush models, then effects on wintering grounds could be simulated separately from Landis and ALCES Online scenarios and used to adjust population projections of Wood Thrush (Hostetler et al., 2015).

Conservation Planning for Wood Thrush: Caveats

The habitat preferences of Wood Thrush (areas with more deciduous forest and/or swamps with small amounts of shrubland) result in them being unevenly distributed across the conservation-planning study areas in Ontario, Quebec, New Brunswick, and Nova Scotia. As

such, the highest-ranked areas that are required to maintain at least 50 % of the current Wood Thrush population in a study area occupy much less than 50 % of the study area. As Wood Thrush were predicted to increase from 2020 – 2100 A. D. in all study areas, when future Wood Thrush distribution was considered in addition to current distribution, the amount of the study area estimated as necessary to maintain 50 – 100 % of the current population was less than when only current distribution was considered. In runtime plots for Zonation exercises, the total value of the current density layer – and when present, the future density layer - decreased as an increasing proportion of a landscape’s pixels were “removed” from protection or consideration as habitat, along with any Wood Thrush predicted to occur in the removed pixels. The remaining proportion of the current density layer, representing the current population of Wood Thrush, decreased at a slower rate in Zonation exercises that considered both current and future distributions of Wood Thrush than in exercises that considered only the current distribution. When future distribution is also considered, the highest priority areas for maintaining 50 % of the current Wood Thrush population were contained within the highest-priority areas for maintaining the same percentage when only current Wood Thrush distribution was used to rank locations.

The resulting maps and runtime plots that show the amounts and locations of lands to prioritize as habitat for the current Wood Thrush population appear to show that less land needs to be prioritized when future Wood Thrush distribution is considered as well. There are a few major caveats to this conclusion.

The first caveat is that Zonation exercises that consider future distribution when prioritizing lands are only considering one or a few possible futures, and these future distributions are only as realistic as the assumptions of the land use scenarios and the models used to generate them. The models used in the current study to predict Wood Thrush abundance may or may not be adequate for predicting true habitat quality, so Zonation could be assigning higher priority to sites that support higher Wood Thrush densities but are suboptimal habitats (Battin, 2004). One solution may be to generate models and future scenarios based on Wood Thrush reproductive success and population viability (Bonnot et al., 2013), then use the resulting prediction maps as a layer in Zonation exercises. The climate change and land use simulations in the current study assume certain disturbances occur and do not account for other disturbances that could decrease Wood Thrush habitat (conversion to urban lands and cropland) or increase Wood Thrush habitat (e.g., afforestation, habitat restoration) (Bonnot et al., 2013). Here, solutions could include running additional land use scenarios to assess the effect of these activities on future Wood Thrush distributions.

The second caveat is that the maps showing the amount and location of lands to prioritize as important habitats are based on the ranks of each location and do not show densities. In the Zonation exercises that were run, ranks were a function of current (and sometimes future) predicted densities of Wood Thrush, measures of uncertainty (standard deviation) in the density estimates and known occurrence locations of Wood Thrush. Locations received higher ranks if they supported known occurrences or higher current or future densities and lower estimates of uncertainty. Thus, while higher-ranked areas tended to support higher predicted densities, the relationship is not a one-on-one relationship. A location could receive a lower rank (e.g. not as

important for protecting at least 50 % of the current population) in a Zonation exercise considering both current and future distributions and that location could still support a higher Wood Thrush density in the future and be valuable habitat than the same location in a Zonation exercise that only considers current population. This possibility is plausible since Wood Thrush was projected to increase in all the future scenarios used in the Zonation exercises. Observing that ranks are influenced by but not necessarily strongly correlated with density may also help to explain why the amount of land to be prioritized as habitat for the current population does not strongly differ among Zonation exercises that considered the best-case, medium-case, and worst-case future population projections from a given study area.

A third caveat for those Zonation exercises that considered future Wood Thrush distribution is that the current Wood Thrush density was included and strongly favoured when prioritizing locations as habitat by down-weighting the future density. The reasons for doing so are 1) that we have greater confidence in current density estimates than future population projections, and 2) when prioritizing lands for habitat, it is important to consider where SAR currently exist: if current habitats are not protected the species may not survive long enough to settle in the best future habitats (Westwood et al., 2020). However, because current density and known occurrences are so strongly weighted in the Zonation exercises in the current study, the highest-ranked sites tend to be located within the same areas as when only current density and known occurrences are considered in other Zonation exercises. This issue may be addressed by running Zonation exercises where only the future distribution is considered.

Code

Analysis scripts used in running GW models and processing results from GW models are located at <https://github.com/LionelLeston/GWmodel-WoodThrush>. Analysis scripts used in running BRT models for predicting Wood Thrush abundance from Landis scenarios, and processing results from those Landis scenarios and Zonation conservation planning exercises are located at <https://github.com/LionelLeston/riskAssessment-WoodThrush-Landis>. Analysis scripts used in running BRT models for predicting Wood Thrush abundance from the ALCES Online scenario in Ontario, and processing results from that scenario and Zonation conservation planning exercises in Ontario are located at <https://github.com/LionelLeston/riskAssessment-WoodThrush-ALCESOnline>. Data used in all models is either available from the Boreal Avian Modelling Project or via links to the original data sources, provided within the folder structure of the R project in each repository.

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Appendix I of Technical Methods and Results Report (EC Contract No. – N°de contrat EC3000713776

Summary data used for setting disturbance parameters for individual Forest Management Units and Bird Conservation Region 13, along with individual project and ALCES Online baseline scenario settings used for projecting future habitat availability (2020 – 2070) for Wood Thrush within its estimated range in Ontario. Note: 2010 is treated as year 0 in all ALCES Online simulations, but vegetation and footprint data used in simulations are updated to 2020, therefore while the simulations are described in the scenarios as running from 2010 – 2060, they are projecting land use change from 2020 – 2070.

Summary Tables for Setting Parameters for ALCES Online Baseline Scenario

Table 1. Decadal harvested area and mean harvest size from clear-cutting in Ontario Forest Management Units within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario.

Unit Name	Total Decadal Clear-cut Area (ha)	Mean Clear-cut Size (ha)	Maximum Clear-cut Size (ha)
Abitibi River Forest	33167	12	229
Algoma Forest	5151	7	130
Algonquin Park Forest	1985	4	61
Bancroft-Minden Forest	6621	8	127
Black Spruce Forest	2455	7	138
French-Severn Forest	1088	10	75
Gordon Cosens Forest	9917	7	172
Hearst Forest	5644	2	83
Kenora Forest	167	9	51
Lakehead Forest	5007	3	82
Mazinaw-Lanark Forest	1253	2	35
Nagagami Forest	19421	11	218
Nipissing Forest	17930	12	183
Northshore Forest	22776	9	233
Ottawa Valley Forest	8950	5	79
Pineland Forest	9989	5	111
Romeo Malette Forest	22294	8	187
Spanish Forest	15272	8	267
Sudbury Forest	13257	18	482
Temagami	4466	18	407
Timiskaming Forest	5782	11	142
White River Forest	18342	6	144

Table 2. Decadal harvested area and mean harvest size from shelterwood logging in Ontario Forest Management Units within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario.

Unit Name	Total Decadal Shelterwood Harvest Area (ha)	Mean Shelterwood Harvest Size (ha)	Maximum Shelterwood Harvest Size (ha)
Algoma Forest	9766	13	280
Algonquin Park Forest	27436	4	337
Bancroft-Minden Forest	6953	11	179
French-Severn Forest	21846	12	443
Mazinaw-Lanark Forest	6622	2	47
Nipissing Forest	10597	12	181
Northshore Forest	8337	11	166
Ottawa Valley Forest	7045	6	90
Pineland Forest	28	14	19
Spanish Forest	80	6	41
Sudbury Forest	4420	11	140
Temagami	8	3	5

Table 3. Decadal harvested area and mean harvest size from selective logging in Ontario Forest Management Units within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario.

Unit Name	Total Decadal Selective Logging Harvest Area (ha)	Mean Selective Logging Harvest Size (ha)	Maximum Selective Logging Harvest Size (ha)
Algoma Forest	15375	19	337
Algonquin Park Forest	27581	6	206
Bancroft-Minden Forest	9125	11	227
French-Severn Forest	15761	17	491
Mazinaw-Lanark Forest	4499	2	71
Nipissing Forest	1645	25	173
Northshore Forest	1158	13	78
Ottawa Valley Forest	2044	7	77
Sudbury Forest	129	13	36
Temagami	10	3	4

Table 4. Decadal disturbed area and mean outbreak size associated with mortality of trees from spruce budworm outbreaks in Ontario Forest Management Units and in Bird Conservation Region 13 within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario.

Unit Name	Total Decadal Outbreak Area (ha)	Mean Outbreak Size (ha)	Maximum Outbreak Size (ha)
Abitibi River Forest	32	11	16
Algoma Forest	124	7	20
Bird Conservation Region 13	17,501	15	1,251
French-Severn Forest	1,256	84	373
Gordon Cosens Forest	2,798	8	93
Nipissing Forest	17,579	21	1,144
Northshore Forest	50	4	12
Pineland Forest	175	10	37
Romeo Malette Forest	214	10	45
Spanish Forest	2	2	2
Sudbury Forest	33,531	26	872
Temagami Forest	1,706	14	172

Table 5. Decadal burned area and mean forest fire size from fires in Ontario Forest Management Units within the Wood Thrush range in Ontario.

Unit Name	Total Decadal Burned Area (ha)	Mean Burn Size (ha)	Maximum Burn Size (ha)
Abitibi River Forest	392	131	175
Algoma Forest	3259	1086	1888
Algonquin Park Forest	45	45	45
Boundary Waters Forest	453	10	94
French-Severn Forest	6458	3229	6449
Missinaibi Forest	1724	575	1558
Nipissing Forest	2898	966	2476
Ottawa Valley Forest	973	243	694
Pic Forest	271	271	271
Pineland Forest	193	193	193
Romeo Malette Forest	21804	4361	21332
Spanish Forest	50	50	50
Sudbury Forest	5217	1739	4604
Temagami Forest	7789	865	5624

Timiskaming Forest	1738	869	1606
White River Forest	118	59	60

Abitibi Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276127. Abitibi River Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Abitibi Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)

- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 105,757 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 317,272; 2030: 317,272; 2040: 317,272; 2050: 317,272; 2060: 317,272

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 116,826 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 331,668,289; 2030: 331,668,289; 2040: 331,668,289; 2050: 331,668,289; 2060: 331,668,289

Algoma Forest

Project Setup:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|--|
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Algoma Forest | ● Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU |
| ● Super region: Ontario HD | ● Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276105. Algoma Forest (3) |
| ● User: cws_ontario | ● Simulation increments: Decades |
| ● Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060 | ● Output increments: Decades |
| ● Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200 | |

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Algoma Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Algoma Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 65,390 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 1,242,403; 2030: 1,242,403; 2040: 1,242,403; 2050: 1,242,403; 2060: 1,242,403

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring

- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 190,281 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 157,347,049; 2030: 157,347,049; 2040: 157,347,049; 2050: 157,347,049; 2060: 157,347,049

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 129,181 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 97,660,606; 2030: 97,660,606; 2040: 97,660,606; 2050: 97,660,606; 2060: 97,660,606

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 66,127 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic

- IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 51,512,929; 2030: 51,512,929; 2040: 51,512,929; 2050: 51,512,929; 2060: 51,512,929

Algonquin Forest

Project Setup:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|---|
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest | ● Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU |
| ● Super region: Ontario HD | ● Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276106. Algonquin Forest (1) |
| ● User: cws_ontario | ● Simulation increments: Decades |
| ● Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060 | ● Output increments: Decades |
| ● Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200 | |

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline run 5

- | | |
|---|---|
| ● Project: WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest | ● End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00 |
| ● Popdyn project: ----- | ● Simulation increments: Decadal |
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Algonquin Forest Baseline | ● Output increments: Decadal |
| ● Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks | ● Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS |
| ● Scenario type: Forecast | ● Shared with: Usergroup |
| ● Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00 | ● Is global: Left unchecked |
| | ● Status: ----- |
| | ● Use project rand seed: Left unchecked |

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard

- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 56,740 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 275,812,773; 2030: 275,812,773; 2040: 275,812,773; 2050: 275,812,773; 2060: 275,812,773

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 38,714 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 274,364,511; 2030: 274,364,511; 2040: 274,364,511; 2050: 274,364,511; 2060: 274,364,511

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked

- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 37,812 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 19,851,754; 2030: 19,851,754; 2040: 19,851,754; 2050: 19,851,754; 2060: 19,851,754

Bancroft-Minden Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276109. Bancroft Minden Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Bancroft Minden Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 113,070 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 91,247,935; 2030: 91,247,935; 2040: 91,247,935; 2050: 91,247,935; 2060: 91,247,935

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 108,814 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 65,932,094; 2030: 65,932,094; 2040: 65,932,094; 2050: 65,932,094; 2060: 65,932,094

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard

- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 83,279 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 66,206,930; 2030: 66,206,930; 2040: 66,206,930; 2050: 66,206,930; 2060: 66,206,930

Black Spruce Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276117. Black Spruce Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Black Spruce Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS

- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 67,623 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 24,547,026; 2030: 24,547,026; 2040: 24,547,026; 2050: 24,547,026; 2060: 24,547,026

Boundary Waters Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276125. Boundary Waters Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Boundary Waters Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest – NONE; Fire; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Fire Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Fire, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 96,293 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) < 20, 0.08,
IF ((Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 0.13,
IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 0.22,
IF ((Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 0.5, 0.9))))))
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON

- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 4,525,750; 2030: 4,525,750; 2040: 4,525,750; 2050: 4,525,750; 2060: 4,525,750

French-Severn Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 French Severn Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276131. French Severn Forest (3)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 French Severn Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 French Severn Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked

- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 837,642 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 12,564,640; 2030: 12,564,640; 2040: 12,564,640; 2050: 12,564,640; 2060: 12,564,640

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 173,581 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 157,622,555; 2030: 157,622,555; 2040: 157,622,555; 2050: 157,622,555; 2060: 157,622,555

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)

- Size class: 115,159 (Proportion 1.0)
- Vector mask: NONE
- Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 218,457,230; 2030: 218,457,230; 2040: 218,457,230; 2050: 218,457,230; 2060: 218,457,230

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 96,293 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 10,881,056; 2030: 10,881,056; 2040: 10,881,056; 2050: 10,881,056; 2060: 10,881,056

Gordon Cosens Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276113. Gordon Cosens Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Gordon Cosens Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 77,942 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 27,981,213; 2030: 27,981,213; 2040: 27,981,213; 2050: 27,981,213; 2060: 27,981,213

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled

- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 67,691 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 99,168,203; 2030: 99,168,203; 2040: 99,168,203; 2050: 99,168,203; 2060: 99,168,203

Hearst Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Hearst Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276118. Hearst Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Hearst Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Hearst Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Random (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 23,746 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 56,444,374; 2030: 56,444,374; 2040: 56,444,374; 2050: 56,444,374; 2060: 56,444,374

Kenora Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Kenora Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276111. Kenora Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Kenora Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Kenora Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 92,687 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 1,668,375; 2030: 1,668,375; 2040: 1,668,375; 2050: 1,668,375; 2060: 1,668,375

Lakehead Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276129. Lakehead Forest (3)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest
- Popdyn project: ----
- Name: WOTH 200 Lakehead Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: ----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Random (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 32,833)
 - Size class: 32,833 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 50,069,710; 2030: 50,069,710; 2040: 50,069,710; 2050: 50,069,710; 2060: 50,069,710

Mazinaw-Lanark Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276104. Mazinaw Lanark Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Mazinaw Lanark Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)

- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 21,004 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 44,991,405; 2030: 44,991,405; 2040: 44,991,405; 2050: 44,991,405; 2060: 44,991,405

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Random (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 19,516)
 - Size class: 19,516 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 66,219,887; 2030: 66,219,887; 2040: 66,219,887; 2050: 66,219,887; 2060: 66,219,887

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Random (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 19,300)
 - Size class: 19,300 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic

- IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 12,526,147; 2030: 12,526,147; 2040: 12,526,147; 2050: 12,526,147; 2060: 12,526,147

Missinaibi Forest

Project Setup:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|--|
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest | ● Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU |
| ● Super region: Ontario HD | ● Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276107. Missinaibi Forest (1) |
| ● User: cws_ontario | ● Simulation increments: Decades |
| ● Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060 | ● Output increments: Decades |
| ● Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200 | |

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline run 5

- | | |
|---|---|
| ● Project: WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest | ● End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00 |
| ● Popdyn project: ----- | ● Simulation increments: Decadal |
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Missinaibi Forest Baseline | ● Output increments: Decadal |
| ● Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks | ● Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS |
| ● Scenario type: Forecast | ● Shared with: Usergroup |
| ● Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00 | ● Is global: Left unchecked |
| | ● Status: ----- |
| | ● Use project rand seed: Left unchecked |

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest – NONE; Fire; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Fire Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Fire, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 5,747,293 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) < 20, 0.08,
IF ((Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 0.13,
IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 0.22,
IF ((Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 0.5, 0.9))))))
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 17,241,819; 2030: 17,241,819; 2040: 17,241,819; 2050: 17,241,819; 2060: 17,241,819

Nagagami Forest

Project Setup:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|--|
| ● Name: WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest | ● Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU |
| ● Super region: Ontario HD | ● Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276103. Nagagami Forest (1) |
| ● User: cws_ontario | ● Simulation increments: Decades |
| ● Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060 | ● Output increments: Decades |
| ● Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200 | |

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline run 5

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------|
| ● Project: WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest | ● Popdyn project: ----- |
|-------------------------------------|-------------------------|

- Name: WOTH 200 Nagagami Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 32,833)
 - Size class: 107,598 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 194,214,825; 2030: 194,214,825; 2040: 194,214,825; 2050: 194,214,825; 2060: 194,214,825

Nipissing Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276130. Nipissing Forest (3)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest
- Popdyn project: ----
- Name: WOTH 200 Nipissing Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: ----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 211,281 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 175,786,000; 2030: 175,786,000; 2040: 175,786,000; 2050: 175,786,000; 2060: 175,786,000

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 253,015 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 16,445,960; 2030: 16,445,960; 2040: 16,445,960; 2050: 16,445,960; 2060: 16,445,960

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 119,601 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 105,960,000; 2030: 105,960,000; 2040: 105,960,000; 2050: 105,960,000; 2060: 105,960,000

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled

- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 122,891 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 179,297,908; 2030: 179,297,908; 2040: 179,297,908; 2050: 179,297,908; 2060: 179,297,908

Northshore Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Northshore Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276102. Northshore Forest (2)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Northshore Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Northshore Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE

- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 41,426 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 497,115; 2030: 497,115; 2040: 497,115; 2050: 497,115; 2060: 497,115

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 130,141 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 11,582,571; 2030: 11,582,571; 2040: 11,582,571; 2050: 11,582,571; 2060: 11,582,571

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 107,020 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - $IF ((Forest\ Age\ 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense\ Deciduous\ ON + Dense\ Mixed\ ON) > 50, 1, 0)$
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 83,368,314; 2030: 83,368,314; 2040: 83,368,314; 2050: 83,368,314; 2060: 83,368,314

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 89,755 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - $IF ((Forest\ Age\ 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense\ Conifer\ ON + Dense\ Deciduous\ ON + Sparse\ or\ Undifferentiated\ Forest\ ON) > 50, 1, 0)$
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 227,759,644; 2030: 227,759,644; 2040: 227,759,644; 2050: 227,759,644; 2060: 227,759,644

Ottawa Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276124. Ottawa Forest (3)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Ottawa Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 67,445 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON

- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 20,435,909; 2030: 20,435,909; 2040: 20,435,909; 2050: 20,435,909; 2060: 20,435,909

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 59,202 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 70,450,000; 2030: 70,450,000; 2040: 70,450,000; 2050: 70,450,000; 2060: 70,450,000

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 51,825 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 89,502,340; 2030: 89,502,340; 2040: 89,502,340; 2050: 89,502,340; 2060: 89,502,340

Pic Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Pic Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276110. Pic Forest (2)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Pic Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Pic Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest – NONE; Fire; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Fire Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Fire, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)

- Size class: 2,710,707 (Proportion 1.0)
- Vector mask: NONE
- Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) < 20, 0.08,
 - IF ((Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 0.13,
 - IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 0.22,
 - IF ((Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 0.5, 0.9))))))

- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 2,710,707; 2030: 2,710,707; 2040: 2,710,707; 2050: 2,710,707; 2060: 2,710,707

Pineland Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Pineland Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276115. Pineland Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Pineland Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Pineland Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE

- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 97,409 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 1,753,364; 2030: 1,753,364; 2040: 1,753,364; 2050: 1,753,364; 2060: 1,753,364

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 140,822 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 281,645; 2030: 281,645; 2040: 281,645; 2050: 281,645; 2060: 281,645

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 51,570 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 99,891,147; 2030: 99,891,147; 2040: 99,891,147; 2050: 99,891,147; 2060: 99,891,147

Romeo Mallette Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276108. Romeo Mallette Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest
- Name: WOTH 200 Romeo Mallette Forest Baseline
- Popdyn project: -----

- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 97,396 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 2,142,711; 2030: 2,142,711; 2040: 2,142,711; 2050: 2,142,711; 2060: 2,142,711

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 76,639 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE

- Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 222,942,202; 2030: 222,942,202; 2040: 222,942,202; 2050: 222,942,202; 2060: 222,942,202

Spanish Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Spanish Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276116. Spanish Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Spanish Forest
- Popdyn project: ----
- Name: WOTH 200 Spanish Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: ----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn

- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE

- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 21,289 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 21,289; 2030: 21,289; 2040: 21,289; 2050: 21,289; 2060: 21,289

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 57,226 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 801,163; 2030: 801,163; 2040: 801,163; 2050: 801,163; 2060: 801,163

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE

- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 80,211 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 152,721,310; 2030: 152,721,310; 2040: 152,721,310; 2050: 152,721,310; 2060: 152,721,310

Sudbury Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276112. Sudbury Forest (2)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Sudbury Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 258,527 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 335,309,332; 2030: 335,309,332; 2040: 335,309,332; 2050: 335,309,332; 2060: 335,309,332

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 129,272 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 1,292,723; 2030: 1,292,723; 2040: 1,292,723; 2050: 1,292,723; 2060: 1,292,723

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest

- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 107,019 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 44,198,868; 2030: 44,198,868; 2040: 44,198,868; 2050: 44,198,868; 2060: 44,198,868

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 180,371 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 132,572,456; 2030: 132,572,456; 2040: 132,572,456; 2050: 132,572,456; 2060: 132,572,456

Temagami Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Temagami Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276101. Temagami Forest (3)

- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Temagami Forest
- Popdyn project: ----
- Name: WOTH 200 Temagami Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: ----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging; Shelterwood harvest; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 143,333 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 17,056,640; 2030: 17,056,640; 2040: 17,056,640; 2050: 17,056,640; 2060: 17,056,640

Selective Logging Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class: 26,103 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 104,433; 2030: 104,433; 2040: 104,433; 2050: 104,433; 2060: 104,433

Shelterwood Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class: 25,185 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON + Dense Mixed ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 75,555; 2030: 75,555; 2040: 75,555; 2050: 75,555; 2060: 75,555

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add

- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 181,555 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 44,662,433; 2030: 44,662,433; 2040: 44,662,433; 2050: 44,662,433; 2060: 44,662,433

Timiskaming Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276098. Timiskaming Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 Timiskaming Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 108,078 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 57,821,668; 2030: 57,821,668; 2040: 57,821,668; 2050: 57,821,668; 2060: 57,821,668

White River Forest

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 White River Forest
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4444. WOTH x FMU
- Study area: (WOTH x FMU) 276114. White River Forest (1)
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline, WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 White River Forest
- Popdyn project: -----
- Name: WOTH 200 White River Forest Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: -----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks – NONE; Clear-cut harvest; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest – NONE

Clear-cut Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 10 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 36000)
 - Size class: 55,837 (Proportion 1.0)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON + Dense Deciduous ON + Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON) > 50, 1, 0)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 183,423,369; 2030: 183,423,369; 2040: 183,423,369; 2050: 183,423,369; 2060: 183,423,369

Bird Conservation Region 13 (Outside Forest Management Units)

Project Setup:

- Name: WOTH 200 BCR 13
- Super region: Ontario HD
- User: cws_ontario
- Timeline: 1610 – 1910 – 2010 – 2060
- Resolution (in m): Ontario HD: 200
- Region scheme: 4451. WOTH x BCR
- Study area: (WOTH x BCR) 276096. BCR13
- Simulation increments: Decades
- Output increments: Decades

Predisturbance Indicators Tracked:

Burn, Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Forest Age 2020, Forest Origin ON, Harvest, Sparse or Undifferentiated Forest ON, Treed Wetland ON

Baseline Scenario:

WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline, WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline run 2, WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline run 3, WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline run 4, WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline run 5

- Project: WOTH 200 BCR 13
- Popdyn project: ----
- Name: WOTH 200 BCR 13 Baseline
- Description: Baseline harvest and budworm outbreaks
- Scenario type: Forecast
- Start time: 2010-01-01 00:00:00
- End time: 2060-12-31 00:00:00
- Simulation increments: Decadal
- Output increments: Decadal
- Created in usergroup: Ontario CWS
- Shared with: Usergroup
- Is global: Left unchecked
- Status: ----
- Use project rand seed: Left unchecked

Standard Actions:

Budworm outbreaks; Clear-cut harvest – NONE; Fire – NONE; Selective logging – NONE; Shelterwood harvest – NONE; Woodlot harvest

Budworm Outbreaks:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Burn
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Pest, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 20 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 1.0) (Max per pixel 20000)
 - Size class 1: 185,000 (Proportion 0.83)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - $IF ((Forest\ Age\ 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense\ Conifer\ ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1$
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
 - Size class 2: 750,000 (Proportion 0.13)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - $IF ((Forest\ Age\ 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense\ Conifer\ ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1$
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
 - Size class 3: 1,480,000 (Proportion 0.03)

- Vector mask: NONE
- Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
- Size class 4: 2,500,000 (Proportion 0.01)
- Vector mask: NONE
- Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 60, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Conifer ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 175,010,000; 2030: 175,010,000; 2040: 175,010,000; 2050: 175,010,000; 2060: 175,010,000

Woodlot Harvest Action:

- Action type: Standard
- Schedule mode: Add
- Schedule indicator: Harvest
- Schedule expr: Left unfilled
- Is yield: Checked
- Yield Type: Recurring
- Add Thematic Filter: NONE
- Add Transition: Update Forest Origin ON to Cut, Set Data Forest Age 2020 to 60 Year(s)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 0.48) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class 1: 50,000 (Proportion 0.956)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
 - Size class 2: 450,000 (Proportion 0.042)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
 - Size class 3: 1,000,000 (Proportion 0.002)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic
 - IF ((Forest Age 2020) > 80, 1, 0) * IF ((Dense Deciduous ON) > 50, 1, 0) * 1
(=Regional modifier: 1 by default, 0 if a pixel is within one of the FMUs)
- Add Allocation: Clustered (Proportion 0.23) (Max per pixel 10000)
 - Size class 1: 50,000 (Proportion 0.956)
 - Vector mask: NONE
 - Raster mask: Dynamic

- Eligible Indicators: Dense Conifer ON, Dense Deciduous ON, Dense Mixed ON, Plantations - Cultivated
- Schedule (Period: Value): 2020: 5,431,000,000; 2030: 5,431,000,000; 2040: 5,431,000,000; 2050: 5,431,000,000; 2060: 5,431,000,000